

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D1.3 Report on 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies v1.0

Document Summary Information

Grant Agreement No	951867	Acronym	5G-ROUTES
Full Title	Report on 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies v1.0		
Start Date	01/09/2020	Duration	36 months
Project URL	https://www.5g-routes.eu		
Deliverable	D1.3		
Work Package	WP1		
Contractual due date	31.12.2020	Actual submission date	29.12.2020
Nature	R	Dissemination Level	PU
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Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
V0.1	06.10.2020	0	Initial Deliverable Structure	A.Lindenbergs
v0.2	24.11.2020	0	Updated Deliverable Structure	A.Lindenbergs
v0.3	17.12.2020	30	Draft content	LMT: A.Lindenbergs, K.Kalnins, D.Krievina, A.Meirans Airbus: Helmut Zaglauer
V0.4	18.12.2020	70	First internal review	LMT: A.Lindenbergs, K.Kalnins, D.Krievina, A.Meirans LMT review team: A.Mežciema, V.Beinārs, A.Benders
V0.5	18.12.2020	70	Pre-review meeting with WP1. Content added after telco.	LMT: A.Lindenbergs
V0.6	21.12.2020	70	Comments of peer reviewer M. Krupp (Telia)	Telia: Margus Krupp LMT: A.Lindenbergs
V1.0	29.12.2020	100	Final version	LMT: A.Lindenbergs, D.Krievina

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
5G	5th generation
NR V2X	Direct communication based on a New Radio
A-GNSS	Assisted Global Navigation Satellite System
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALKS	Automated lane keeping systems
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
CAD	Connected and automated driving
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport System
CSMS	Cyber security management systems
DSSAD	Data storage system for automated driving
ECU	Electronic Control Unit
EDR	Event data recorder
eMBB	enhanced Mobile Broadband
EU	European Union
FRMCS	Future railway mobile Communication System
gNB	5G base station
GRSG	UNECE Working Party on General Safety
GSM-R	Global System for Mobile Communication - Railways
GSR	EU General Safety Regulation
HARQ	Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request
ICS	Intersection Controller System
IoT	Internet Of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIDAR	Light Detection And Ranging

LPP	Location Positioning Protocol
LTE	Long Term Evolution
LTE LPPa	LT Positioning Protocol A
MEC	Mobile Edge Computing
MFCN	Mobile and Fixed Communications Networks
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
NR	New Radio
OBU	On Board Unit
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OTDOA	Observed Time Difference Of Arrival positioning
PPK	Post Processed Kinematic positioning
PPP	Precise Point Positioning
RTK	Real Time Kinematic positioning
QZSS	Quai-Zenith Satellite System
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RSU	Road Side Units
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
TDD	Time Division Duplex
UC	Use Case
UCC	Use Case Category
UE	User Equipment
UHD	Ultra High Definition
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
V2D	Vehicle-to-device
V2G	Vehicle-to-grid
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2N	Vehicle-to-network
V2P	Vehicle-to-pedestrian
V2V	Vehicle-to-vehicle
V2x	Vehicle-to-everything
VR	Virtual Reality
VS	Visualisation System
VRU	Vulnerable Road User

1. Executive Summary

The aim of deliverable 1.3 is to summarise 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan giving a snapshot view of assumptions, challenges and opportunities identified in initial stage of the 5G-ROUTES project. The report is based on MNO's perspective for setting up a new 5G trial network for large scale trials of Northern Europe. The project title proposes a longer-term deployment strategy, however, such strategy is dependent on delays of 3GPP releases, i.e. R.16 to 2021 and R.17 to 2022/2023 and associated uncertainties. This restricts availability and vendor readiness to provide the technology before 2023 and to propose longer term strategy for deployment at least in initial phase of the project.

Cross-border 5G communication demonstration gives several challenges which should be addressed during the deployment phase of the project. Within the report a blending of use case requirements, enabling technologies and technical framework requirements are analysed alongside the technical challenges faced by geopolitical limitations and legislations. All above mentioned aspects are carefully summarised and pinned for further risk assessment type of analysis, identifying opportunities for deployment of the use cases, in particular at border crossing locations. The report also includes an analysis of Latvia, Estonia and Finland regulations in both CAM and radio spectrum, aiming to set the legislative landscape.

Finally, the report presents the 5G-ROUTES demonstration 5G network deployment plan for large scale and localised trial sites in Latvia, Estonia and Finland.

2. Introduction

5G-Routes aims to prepare the ground for covering all major cities in Latvia, Estonia and Finland, including all major transport paths (roads, railways and shipways) traversing these countries with 5G connectivity by 2023, thus aligning with and realising the long-term roadmap of the European CEF programme. Collaboration opportunities will be sought with other neighbouring EU member states in an attempt to extend the deployment plan to cover other EU countries. The plan will be complemented with a set of new commercially justified and viable business models (telco investing, co-investment telco/automotive sectors, multi-party investment including road operators, public financing from member states, cooperation options under CEF, etc.) for the deployment and delivery of 5G-enabled cross-border V2X CAM services. A clear migration plan for the use and co-existence of 5G enabling technologies with other existing technologies, such as IEEE802p, C-V2X for CAM services will also be developed.

2.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map 5G-ROUTES's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1. Adherence to 5G-ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D1.3	Report on 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies v1.0	This document	
TASKS			
T1.2 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and long-term strategies for full scale deployment of 5G infrastructure	Major KPIs that are relevant to network planning and deployment will be included and considered to meet the specific UC criteria.	Section 3.2	Section 3.2 describes network and service-level KPIs that are defined in D1.1 that are relevant for network planning.
	Main 5G Technologies covered in 5G-ROUTES project will be described and tested impact on UC testing.	Chapter 4	High level description of 3GPP Releases 16 & 17 and main features and functionalities.
	A detailed overview of the current situation of spectrum availability in Latvia, Estonia and Finland will be carried out.	Section 5.1	The section summarises the availability of frequencies at present and the scheduled auctions.
	A detailed overview of the current legislative situation of CAM in Latvia, Estonia and Finland will be carried out.	Section 5.2	Section 5.2 gives an insight of CAM legislation.
	A detailed analysis of 5G-ROUTES sites will be carried out, identifying network development capabilities.	Chapter 6	Section 6.1-6.6 provide an assessment of the existing infrastructure of MNOs at the planned test sites.

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable describes how a 5G deployment plan will be established and what information is being used and analysed, such as availability of frequencies, the required network features, legislation impact on 5G deployment etc. Sequence of deliverable development is shown in Figure 1 and relation between D1.3 and D1.4 as well.

The report includes the following chapters:

Chapter 3 provides a brief description of each use and summary of relevant KPIs for network architecture development and necessary 5G features selection.

Chapter 4 gives a common insight into readiness of technologies, features and 5G releases in overall.

Chapter 5 covers analysis of spectrum regulation and availability in Latvia, Estonia and Finland, describes CAM legislative framework and gives insight of investment models carried out in previously mentioned countries.

Chapter 6 describes availability of existing infrastructure and opportunities of network development in trial sites.

Chapter 7 will summarise 5G-ROUTES deployment options and plan.

KPIs and Use case descriptions are base information to start the development of deployment plan, this information will be described and analysed in D1.1, but summary will be included in this deliverable as one part of necessary information to define and describe network requirements and necessary 5G features. To achieve full view on network architecture, analysis of trial site locations, infrastructure readiness and spectrum conditions is crucial. The output will cover overall 5G network architectures and specifications deployed in the trial sites.

* - Use cases description & KPIs definition from D1.1

Figure 1. Sequence of deliverable development

Figure 2 gives an insight of dependencies and relations to other deliverables and working packages.

Figure 2. Deliverable dependencies with other deliverables and working packages

3. Use cases & KPIs

The 4G network already provides an opportunity to test a variety of CAM applications that have basic requirements for network KPIs. 5G-ROUTES aims to validate 5G as a true enabler of innovative CAM services that cannot be realised by today's wireless communication technologies due to stringent requirements, such as ultra-low latency (<10ms), ultra-high reliability (error rate 10^{-5}), large density of connected devices (up to 1m users per km²), high throughput (>100Mbps), high positioning accuracy (within 10cm), extended coverage area, etc., within a single MNO's network and also across different MNOs, terrestrial-satellite networks, countries, telco vendors, vehicles, modes of transport and end-user devices.

Defining network requirements and developing a network deployment plan is based on UC requirements and corresponding defined KPIs. This section contains short description of 5G-ROUTES use cases and the main aggregates needed for 5G deployment plan. Information will be updated following the 5G-ROUTES tests on localized and large-scale trials. More detailed description and definition of 5G-ROUTES UC and KPIs are described in D1.1 "Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM".

3.1 Use cases high-level description

All use cases will be demonstrated over 5G in real-world field trials, to measure the performance improvement and to realise 5G potential, based on the target network and service-level KPIs. All use cases are divided in five main categories highlighted below with high-level description on each use case.

3.1.1 Automated Cooperative Driving

Focus on automated driving use cases where increased level of automation of the vehicle functions and a reduction of the involvement of the driver will be tested to reach highly automated cooperating driving.

UC 1.1: Dynamic vehicles platooning

Description: Dynamic vehicles platooning enables to dynamically form a group of vehicles travelling together. All vehicles in platoon (SAE level 4 automation) receive periodic data from leading vehicle (SAE level 1 automation). This use case will be tested with extremely short distance between vehicles at high speeds, up to 90 km/h in cross-border or virtual cross border trial sites, meaning that gap between cars is milliseconds in translation to time.

Figure 3. Dynamic vehicles platooning

UC 1.2: Cooperative lane change

Description: Vehicle should be able to manoeuvre in an automated manner: automatically change lanes in highways when appropriate. For this, the interaction with the surrounding and the cooperation with other vehicles in the vicinity is of absolute importance, especially in the case of blind spots. All nearby vehicles are informed about the intentions of the vehicle to perform safe lane change and accordingly reduce their speeds.

Figure 4. Cooperative lane change

UC 1.3: See-Through view for safe automated overtake

Description: See-Through helps the automated vehicle to take informed decisions, based on the information received real-time UHD video feed from the vehicle in front, taking into consideration a number of parameters including potential hazards, such as an oncoming remote vehicle in the passing lane or a lack of room in front of the leading remote vehicle) for a safe overtake without the engagement of the driver.

Figure 5. See-Through view for safe automated overtake

3.1.2 Awareness Driving

The aim is to provide reliable data sharing on road conditions, such as increased real-time traffic video streams and controls at complex crossings, using V2X communications such as location, speed, driving pathways, VRU to ensure safe passing and preventing collisions, and to ensure user comfort in traffic jams during automated driving in time.

UC 2.1 Real-time traffic information and cooperative intersection collision control

Description: On intersections, traffic-flow is complex due to the driving behaviour of involved drivers. In this particular and complex use case, an intelligent AI-based Intersection Controller System (ICS) installed at the intersection, enables both the detection and prevention of potential collisions in real-time as well as more efficient operation of the intersection by notifying approaching vehicles about signal phase and timing, dynamically instructing them to adjust their speed and coordinating the traffic flow according to the actual traffic conditions.

Figure 6. Real-time traffic information and cooperative intersection collision control

UC 2.2 Traffic jam chauffeur

Description: Use case with highly automated vehicles (up to SAE level 4) on cross-border, where a driver is not involved. The scenario includes vehicles operating on roads shared with other vehicles, pedestrians, and cyclists, all following a designated route towards the border junction. The traffic jam chauffeur application would make automated driving in traffic jams or stop and go conditions more convenient. The application can steer the vehicle and its brakes in an automated way up to 70 km/h, monitoring the speed of the preceding vehicle and surroundings at the same time through several sensor sources.

Figure 7. Traffic jam chauffeur

3.1.3 Sensing driving

Aim is to enable connected vehicles to share sensing observations and environmental information for related vehicles in order to obtain better understanding of the situation, in particular the absence of information VRUs outside the line of direct vision of drivers, and the development of preventive maintenance system using forecasting analysis, the provision of long-term maintenance and repair services throughout the life of vehicles.

UC 3.1 Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness

Description: Sensor info sharing enables the exchange of raw or processed data gathered through local sensors or live video data among vehicles, Road Site Units (RSU), UEs of pedestrians and V2X application servers, in order to achieve cooperative situation awareness. The On Board Unit (OBU) system of the vehicle collects sensor information and process it to react to situations based on specific parameters, such as cruising speed, the distance from a remote obstacle, the presence of passing vehicle in the blind spot and others.

UC 3.2 Connected maintenance

Description: Use case provided by the collection and real time processing of vehicle sensor data to monitor the health status of certain vehicular elements. AR/VR can be used in conjunction with the usage of the sensors for remote assessment of maintenance issues in order to have enhanced awareness.

UC 3.3 Vulnerable Road User (VRU) Collision Avoidance

Description: Interaction of vehicles with VRUs (e.g. pedestrians, disabled people in wheelchairs, people with sight impairments, pets, bicycles, motorcycles) especially at cross walks and spots without line of sight. A critical requirement for is the real-time accuracy of the positioning information covering pedestrians, cyclists, and vehicles. VRU collision avoidance application has to issue warning, after calculating the trajectories of vehicles and VRUs, by using the geometry of the intersection, the road and its surroundings and determine the risk of collision.

3.1.4 Uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go

This category aims to enable passengers to benefit from the high-performance capabilities of 5G networks while travelling and crossing the borders of EU Member States. Applications in this category include multi-user gaming and 3D virtual co-operation on the move.

UC 4.1 360o Immersive multi-user gaming on the go

Description: Strong increase is expected in UHD multimedia usage, as it becomes immersive and highly interactive, to provide media consumption and content and ambience adapting on the move. Gaming will expand into full 360o immersive multi-sensorial environment, resulting in more realistic experience, improved ability for users to collaborate and without any limitation on the number of simultaneous players. Apart from ultra-fast connections and low latencies, 360o immersive multi-user gaming on the go requires a uniform user experience. Collaborative multi-user video gaming and AR/VR applications will be tested on the move crossing the border.

UC 4.2 3D real-time virtual collaboration on the move

Description: High resolution and high dynamic range videos transmitting enable new real time audio-visual experiences for users. 3D virtual video conference will be tested on the go during entire journey: activating content within autonomous vehicle and afterwards crossing border via railway (Latvia – Estonia border crossing) or ferry (Estonia – Finland).

3.1.5 Multimodal services

It is important to have uninterrupted and seamless service delivery to passengers and visibility of tracked goods through different modes of transport, when changing vehicles or trains to onboard ship liners for journey continuation. These use cases focus on seamless logistics processes, goods tracking, multimodal management of passengers and freight, plus telemetry operations of railways with FRMCS (key enabler for rail transport digitalisation).

UC 5.1 Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics

Description: Goods tracking and online data is important for multimodal cross border logistics. The Gulf of Finland between Estonia and Finland has limited 2G/3G/4G mobile connectivity and therefore, scalable IoT-based tracking is currently not feasible. The aim is to validate effectiveness and continuous visibility of goods tracking throughout multimodal journey of goods traversing multiple EU member states over terrestrial as well as maritime transport. Tests will be performed from Latvia to Estonia and continuation of the journey to a ferry across the Gulf of Finland from Tallinn to Helsinki.

UC 5.2 5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight

Description: Use case comes in two phases: First focuses on the cross-border communication and provides mechanisms for notifications on approaching passengers and freight and assignment of necessary resources in the destination network. Second focuses on multimodality including unloading of freight from trucks and/or railways and loading them to ships in addition to passenger's movement. Automated checking of freight (towards zero-touch), conducting logistics operations and informing authorities is part of this use case.

UC 5.3 FRMCS telemetry operation

Description: FRMCS is set to become the global standard for railway communications. Use case focuses on telemetry operation to allow a certain level of independence between railway applications and underlying transport system, as well as improving service availability. FRMCS equipment adapts the transmission of the telemetry data session to the most QoS effective 5G radio RAN station, thus ensuring uninterrupted and continuous telemetry session whilst the train is on-route.

3.1.6 Classification of use cases

The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) has classified 5G services in three usage scenarios, each having different requirements and communication needs. 5G-ROUTES use cases are classified by these scenarios in D1.1 as shown in Table 2. This classification provides an overall insight into the direction of possible network requirements:

- mMTC** (*massive Machine Type Communications*) – high connection density, extended coverage;
- URLCC** (*Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications*) – ultra low latency, high reliability, high availability;
- eMBB** (*enhanced Mobile Broadband*) –high data rate, extreme throughput, enhanced spectral efficiency;

Classification plays important role on network planning, necessary 5G features, architecture and overall 5G network deployment. Work on more detailed specification is ongoing and will be included in Network requirements in this deliverable.

Table 2. Use case by ITU scenarios classification

Nr	Use Case	mMTC	URLCC	eMBB
1.1	Dynamic vehicles platooning		M	
1.2	Cooperative lane change		M	
1.3	See-Through view for safe automated overtake		S	M
2.1	Intersection collision control		M	
2.2	Traffic jam chauffeur		M	
3.1	Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness		M	
3.2	Connected maintenance	M		
3.3	VRU collision avoidance		M	
4.1	360 degree immersive multi-user gaming on the go		M	
4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the move		S	M
5.1	Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics	M		
5.2	5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight	M		S
5.3	FRMCS telemetry operation	M		

3.1.7 Initial trial sites for use cases

Initially use case testing were planned in three trial sites (Figure 8) all located on cross-border corridor “Via Baltica North”:

- road border crossing between Latvia and Estonia located in Valka-Valga;
- railway border crossing between Latvia and Estonia located in Valka-Valga;
- sea crossing between Estonia and Finland, port in Tallinn and port in Helsinki.

Figure 8. Initial trial sites

In total 14 new 5G base stations planned to implement and relevant 5G infrastructure will be installed in order to validate 5G-ROUTES use cases. Valka-Valga will cover autonomous driving, infotainment services and multimodal services use cases involving vehicles and railways. Based on initial plan, four base stations need to be installed in Valka, four in Valga and two additional base small cells on each railway wagon. In Estonia – Finland trial site, two additional bases stations will be installed in Tallinn port area, one in Helsinki port and small cell in ferry related to Multimodal services and Infotainment use cases involving vehicles or railways and ferry as well. To ensure continued connectivity without service interruption on all cross-border use cases, satellite 5G connectivity will be provided via Ku-band geosynchronous and LEO satellites and integrated with MNOs 5G CNs to support handover.

Based on discussions among 5G-ROUTES partners on the planned trial sites as well as on the first study and analysis of locations, a new trial site will be included for consideration to provide CAM tests. Initial plan is to install two 5G base stations, one will be provided by LMT, the other by Telia. In that manner virtual cross-border will be created in a closed area, which is a unique solution for safe testing of use cases. The Table 3 shows the summary where each UC is planned to be tested.

Table 3. Use cases and trial site locations

Nr	Use Case	Road Valka-Valga	Railway Valka-Valga	Tallinn-Helsinki	Bikernieki race track*
1.1	Dynamic vehicles platooning				X
1.2	Cooperative lane change				X
1.3	See-Through view for safe automated overtake				X
2.1	Intersection collision control	X			
2.2	Traffic jam chauffeur	X			X
3.1	Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness	X			
3.2	Connected maintenance	X			
3.3	VRU collision avoidance	X			X
4.1	360-degree immersive multi-user gaming on the go		X		
4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the move		X		
5.1	Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics			X	
5.2	5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight		X	X	
5.3	FRMCS telemetry operation		X		

* - New trial site in 5G-ROUTES project, not for Large scale trials

3.2 KPIs related to network planning and deployment

Each use case is associated with a specific set of requirements and network-level and service-level KPIs. This section includes general KPIs which are relevant for 5G network architecture and deployment. KPI detailed description is available in D1.1 “Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM” and methodologies of KPI measurements in D1.5 “Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM”. There is still ongoing process of KPIs definition based on use cases and this section will be updated on actual information.

3.2.1 Network KPIs

Network KPIs are related to the 5G communication network, describing the requirements for information exchange between road users, and between the users on the move and the infrastructure. Such KPIs include throughput, mobility, latency, connection density, reliability, positioning accuracy, handover time.

Table 4. Network level KPIs

Use Case Category	ID	Title	Network KPIs							
			Data rate (Mbps)	Mobility (km/h)	E2E latency (ms)	Jitter (ms)	Density (vehicles /Km2)	Reliability (%)	Positioning accuracy (m)	Tho (ms)
1 - Automated Cooperative Driving	1.1	Dynamic vehicles platooning	N/A	<200	5	<0.5	>2 000	>99.99	<1	<10
	1.2	Cooperative lane change	N/A	<200	5	<0.5	>2 000	>99.99	<1	<10
	1.3	See through view for safe automated overtake	>50	<200	5	<0.5	>2 000	>99.99	<1	<10
2 - Awareness Driving	2.1	Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control	N/A	<150	<20	<0.5	>10 000	>99.99	<1	<10
	2.2	Traffic jam chauffeur	N/A	<150	<100	<0.5	>10 000	>99.99	<1	<10
3 - Sensing Driving	3.1	Sensor info sharing	N/A	<150	<10	<0.5	>2 000	>99.99	<0.5	<10
	3.2	Connected maintenance	<100	<250	<1 000	<0.5	> 10 000	>99.99	N/A	<10
	3.3	VRU collision avoidance	N/A	<100	<20	<0.5	>2 000	>99.99	<0.5	<10
4 - Uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go	4.1	360o immersive multi-user gaming on the go	>100	<300	<10	<1	>10 000	>99	N/A	<10
	4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go	<200	<300	<20	<1	>10 000	>99	N/A	<10
5 - Multimodal services	5.1	Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross-border logistics	<250	Not Critical	Not Critical	Not Critical	<10^6	>99.9	<1	<10
	5.2	5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight	<250	<150	<20	<1	>10 000	>99.99	<1	<10
	5.3	FRMCS telemetry operation	<300	<100	<20	<1	-	>99.99	-	<10

3.2.2 Service-level KPIs

The service-level KPIs are related to CAM services, describing the behaviour of the services for the users and goods on the move, e.g. vehicle drivers, vehicle, railway operation, railway and maritime passengers, cargo. Such KPIs include service continuity, service interruption time, Quality of Experience (QoE).

Table 5. Service level KPIs

Use Case Category	ID	Title	Service KPIs				
			Coverage (%)	Availability (%)	Tsi	QOS	QoE (MOS)
1 - Automated Cooperative Driving	1.1	Dynamic vehicles platooning	>99.99	>99.999	<10	-	-
	1.2	Cooperative lane change	>99.99	>99.999	<10	-	-
	1.3	See through view for safe automated overtake	>99.99	>99.999	<10	-	-
2 - Awareness Driving	2.1	Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control	>99.99	>99.999	<10	-	-
	2.2	Traffic jam chauffeur	>99.99	>99.999	<10	-	-
3 - Sensing Driving	3.1	Sensor info sharing	>99.99	>99.999	<10	-	-
	3.2	Connected maintenance	>99.99	>99.999	<10	-	-
	3.3	VRU collision avoidance	>99.99	>99.999	<10	-	-
4 - Uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go	4.1	360o immersive multi-user gaming on the go	>99.99	>99.999	<10	>4.3	10^-9
	4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go	>99.99	>99.999	<10	>4.3	10^-9
5 - Multimodal services	5.1	Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross-border logistics	>99.99	>99.999	<10	>4.3	10^-9
	5.2	5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight	>99.99	>99.999	<10	>4.3	10^-9
	5.3	FRMCS telemetry operation	>99.99	>99.999	<10	>4.3	10^-9

4. Technical framework

The high-level technical approach of 5G-ROUTES shown in Figure 9. The 5G-ROUTES networks will be validated over the emerging 3GPP releases R.16 & R.17, for the 5G RAN and Core. MEC, network slicing, URLLC and other crucial features will be implemented to grant successful test results of predefined use cases.

Figure 9. 5G-ROUTES high-level architectural approach

4.1 3GPP releases and roadmap

5G-ROUTES aims to significantly reduce the ambiguity prior to EU-wide deployment of CAM services on European TEN-T networks. Within North Europe test bed, it will validate capabilities of the following innovative 5G enabling technologies for CAM services (which will be integrated in 5G network equipment at radio, RAN, core network and network orchestration levels). North East Europe is distinguished by highly developed connectivity and low-density population, with potential for fast uptake and introduction of new generation of connectivity.

Reasonable confidence has been established by swift and national wide 3G and 4G introduction in Latvia, Estonia and Finland. A new set of challenges and opportunities arise with latest 3GPP releases i.e. R.16 and R.17. A historical development and new timeline for upcoming releases are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Network standards and they introduction year

Generation	Release	Year	Main features
2G	1	1992	Voice
	2	1995	EFR codec
	96	1997	HSCSD
	97	1998	GPRS
	98	1999	EDGE
3G	99	2000	UMTS 3G, CDMA
	4	2001	all-IP
	5	2002	HSDPA, IP Multimedia Subsystem
	6	2004	HSUPA, Multimedia Broadcast and Multicast Services (MBMS)
	7	2007	HSPA+, NFC
4G	8	2008	All-IP Network, Multiple Input and Multiple Output (MIMO)
	9	2009	Home eNodeB (HeNB)
	10	2011	LTE Advanced, Multi Cell HSDPA
	11	2012	Advanced IP Interconnection
	12	2015	Enhanced Small Cells, Carrier aggregation, Device-to-Device communication (D2D), eMBMS
	13	2016	LTE unlicensed, LTE Advanced Pro
	14	2017	Multimedia Broadcast Supplement, Cell Broadcast Service
5G	15	2018-2019	New Radio (NR), V2X, IP Multimedia Core Network Subsystem (IMS), Future Rail Mobile Communication System (FRMCS)
	16	2018-2020	5G System - Phase 2, V2X Phase 3, Ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communication (URLLC), Satellite Access in 5G, 5G NR Position Services
	17	2020-2022	NR MIMO, RAN slicing, NR Quality of Experience

3GPP release serves as a best practice guideline for system providers to integrate the new features and for vendors to develop and provide a set of new connectivity services. Release 15 has set the scene for updates of mission-critical (MC) communications and MC services functionalities. These functions have evolved from LTE, affecting everything from private communications across broadband to emergency alerts and file distribution for government facilities.

Release 15 allows industries that rely on large-scale MC communications to improve response times, gain better control over device and network software updates and revision management, and assemble teams of responders more quickly and efficiently. Nevertheless, features as Vehicle-to-everything has only drawn and left for much mature update within Release 16.

Source: 3GPP TSG SA#87e, 17-20 March 2020, e-meeting document SP-200222

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Figure 10. 3GPP upcoming release Rel-16 and Rel-17 timeline

Key features (new and updated) in 3GPP Release 16. An overall trend in Rel-16 is to make the 3GPP 5G System (5GS) a communication-enabling platform suitable for wide range of industries (“verticals”), such as transportation (autonomous driving V2X, Railways, Maritime), automated factories, healthcare, public safety and more. In this respect, the versatility and reliability of the 5GS has been further increased to make it industry-grade compatible, with enhancements to Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC), Network Slicing, Edge Computing, Cellular IoT (Internet of Things), Non-Public Networks, Positioning Services and LAN-type services. In addition, the use of 5G as an underlying communication network (i.e. to be used transparently by applications external to the network) has been enhanced, mostly under the work on “Northbound APIs”. Besides all these industrial aspects, other Rel-16 enhancements cover the coexistence of 5G with non-3GPP systems, entertainment (e.g. streaming and media distribution) and network optimisations (e.g. user identity).

The aim of 3GPP Rel.16 is to bring overall system advancements to the “5G Phase 1” described in R.15 as well as functions relevant for addressing the specific communication needs of vertical sectors. One of the verticals directly targeted by the 3GPP is the automotive sector, and 5G-supported vehicle-to everything (V2X) communications considers advanced scenarios that are beyond what is possible with LTE based V2X, primarily in the area of low latency use cases. The general 5G System architecture for 3GPP Rel.16 is specified by the 3GPP SA2 Group in TS 23.501 [25] while the 3GPP document TS 23.287 [26] targets the 5G system architecture enhancements required to support V2X services in 3GPP Rel.16. The latter specification will largely be based on the 3GPP technical report, TR 23.786 “Study on architecture enhancements for Evolved Packet System (EPS) and 5G System to support advanced V2X services” [27]. It should be noted that the relevant V2X specifications pertain to V2V, V2I, V2N and V2P communications using LTE/EPC networks as defined within the previous releases of the 3GPP. Another important new feature of 3GPP Rel.16 will be 5G NR-based positioning services. In the 3GPP Rel.15 specifications, despite the introduction of the new radio access technology, positioning is still handled by the LTE network. Advanced positioning capabilities of 5G NR will be crucial for applications such as emergency services and automated driving, which require advanced positioning. For a wide range of verticals, the main achievements of the 3GPP Rel.16 standards will be the improvements and developments related to industrial

Internet of Things (IoT) and URLLC, which are the other two pillars of the ITU specifications on 5G systems that complement enhanced mobile broadband communications. Offering 5G technology in unlicensed bands and reaching a more accurate level of positioning will pave the way for novel services for existing subscribers of mobile operators as well as various new sectors that will benefit from 5G capabilities. The performance of MIMO systems and power consumption are also on the agenda of the 3GPP Rel.16 standards. The 3GPP document TR 21.916 [33] lists and summarizes all the 3GPP Rel.16 work items (a working document and will be frozen once 3GPP Rel.16 is ready).

First guiding study appearance describing Release 17 is expected in mid-2021, however, some expected features are highly valuable for autonomous demonstration within 5G-ROUTES project.

Some of features relevant to autonomous driving as part of Rel-17 are:

NR Machine Type Communication: In 3GPP, 5G Low Power Wide Area (LPWA) IoT communication is based on the LTE massive MTC (mMTC) technologies: LTE-M and NB-IoT. These technologies cover wide range of use cases and requirements to handle high volumes of IoT devices in a number of use cases, such as smart metering, parking, building management and controlling smart city lights.

3GPP has worked on Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC) mainly as an NR technology so as to meet the stringent reliability and latency requirements of critical MTC (cMTC) use cases, such as robotics and manufacturing. In between, these offerings could be complemented by introducing a new NR device type (“NR Light”) tailored to support industrial wireless sensor networks. NR Light communication is based on NR building blocks, such as numerology and SSB bandwidth, but complemented with enhancements to meet the new requirements such as reduced complexity and lower UE power consumption.

mMIMO: 3GPP has worked on advanced Multiple-Input and Multiple-Output (MIMO) antenna technology over multiple releases. Moving into Rel-17, the focus will be on fixing the issues learned from real-life deployments (instead of standardizing incremental enhancements or enhancements that are not practically implementable).

IAB enhancements: Integrated Access and Backhauling (IAB) solution is expected, introduced in Rel-16, will be further evolved to provide increased efficiency, and therefore support additional use cases. For instance, in disaster scenarios and areas, it can be critical to enable support of ad-hoc and temporary IAB nodes.

Broadcast/Multicast: For broadcast solutions, it is important to look at more advanced use cases compared to the traditional TV broadcast. For example, a public safety scenario benefiting from group call and video broadcast. Furthermore, intelligent transportation systems (ITS) could apply this technology in regard to road conditions and traffic sign/lights information. Therefore, a common framework to enable single and multi-cell (SFN) broadcast is needed.

Sidelink enhancements: Rel-17 is expected to support more use cases for 3GPP based mobile communication. Public safety is the prime example. Support of communication should leverage on as many synergies as possible with ITS. For example, sidelink standardized in ITS use case can be leveraged as broadcast.

NR operation on high frequencies (NR > 52.6 GHz): Operating NR in higher than 52.6 GHz provides great capacity for the operators in specific use cases such as mobile broadband services in indoor and dense urban scenarios. It is important to leverage current NR standards as much as possible also in high frequencies to ensure synergies. Considerable share of spectrum in higher frequencies is unlicensed. Therefore, a commitment to explore (minimum) changes, to support unlicensed operation in those frequencies. With respect to NR-U operation in lower bands, Rel-16 already provides the necessary key components.

4.2 5G features and functionality

3GPP Releases 16 & 17 involve a wide variety of innovative features and functionalities that will be tested in the 5G-ROUTES project in order to ensure that the specific KPIs can be successfully achieved according to use cases. Some of key features without which 5G-ROUTES would be unrealisable are described below.

4.2.1 Network slicing

Network slicing is a concept for running multiple logical customised networks on a shared common physical infrastructure complying with agreed Service Level Agreements (SLAs) for different vertical industry customers (or tenants) and requested functionalities.

Concept of network slicing is a key mechanism for 5G networks, and all 5G-related specifications have been developed by 3GPP from the beginning with the aim to support end-to-end slicing mechanisms, allowing a UE to connect to multiple network slices at the same time. [13]

4.2.2 Mobile Edge Computing

The Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) platform, as defined in ETSI GS MEC 003 [12], offers an environment where MEC applications may discover, advertise, consume and offer MEC services. MEC platforms can be deployed at multiple locations in a network with the chosen location depending on various factors, including required performance criteria (for example, latency), physical deployment constraints, scalability and use case requirements.

4.2.3 NR positioning

Release 16 extends NR to provide native positioning support by introducing RAT-dependent positioning schemes. NR enhanced capabilities provide valuable, enhanced location capabilities. Location accuracy and latency of positioning schemes improve by using wide signal bandwidth in FR1 and FR2. Furthermore, new schemes based on angular/spatial domain are developed to mitigate synchronization errors by exploiting massive antenna systems.

The positioning requirements for regulatory and commercial applications are described in 3GPP TR 38.855 [11]. For regulatory use cases, the following are the minimum performance requirements:

- Horizontal positioning accuracy better than 50 meters for 80% of the UEs.
- Vertical positioning accuracy better than 5 meters for 80% of the UEs.
- End-to-end latency less than 30 seconds.

For commercial use cases, for which the positioning requirements are more stringent, the following are the starting-point performance targets:

- Horizontal positioning accuracy better than 3 meters (indoors) and 10 meters (outdoors) for 80% of the UEs.
- Vertical positioning accuracy better than 3 meters (indoors and outdoors) for 80% of the UEs.
- End-to-end latency less than 1 second.

NR adopts a solution similar to that of LTE LPPa for Broadcast Assistance Data Delivery, which provides support for A-GNSS, RTK and OTDOA positioning methods. PPP-RTK positioning will extend LPP A-GNSS assistance data message based on compact “SSR messages” from QZSS interface specifications. UE-based RAT-dependent DL-only positioning techniques are supported, where the positioning estimation will be done at the UE-based on assistance data provided by the location server. [10]

4.2.4 NR V2X

NR V2X solutions complement existing LTE V2X solutions for advanced automotive industry services. While Release 14 C-V2X introduced sidelink (V2V, V2I, V2P) to support basic safety use cases, Release 16 builds on Release 14/15 by introducing a NR-based sidelink that will enable new advanced safety use cases while also paving the path for autonomous driving. Release 16 supports reliable and efficient multicast communication based on HARQ feedback and uses distance as a new dimension at the physical layer, which enables “on-the-fly” multicast groups based on distance and applications.[9]

NR V2X is designed to coexist and internetwork with LTE V2X. In Figure 11 is shown example of dual connectivity with V2X support. The UE’s V2X communication on the NR sidelink is controlled and configured by the LTE or NR Uu interface, while the UE is configured in EN-DC mode.

Figure 11. LTE-NR Dual connectivity with V2X support

In Figure 12 is an example of NR standalone network with V2X support. The UE’s V2X communication on the NR sidelink is controlled and configured by the gNb through the NR Uu interface. [10]

Figure 12. Standalone NR with V2X support

5. Current 5G deployment plans & readiness in Latvia, Estonia & Finland

5.1 Spectrum regulation and availability

In November 2016 [14], the Radio Spectrum Policy Group (RSPG) provided the first indications for the frequency bands that can be used and which are priority for the development of 5G systems: the 700 MHz band, the 3.5 GHz (3.4-3.8 GHz) band and the 26 GHz band (24.25-27,5 GHz). The 700 MHz frequency band is not a proper 5G band, however, it is internationally recognized as a band that can provide 5G services with wide coverage. Nationwide coverage can be built with the 700 MHz band, but the narrowness of the band means that it cannot implement high-speed 5G data transfer connections. The 3.5 GHz spectrum (3400–3800 MHz) has been identified in Europe as a key frequency band for the construction of 5G networks[15].

In 2019, the latest International Telecommunications Union (ITU) World Radiocommunications Conference identified new radio frequency bands for the International Mobile Telecommunications Administration (IMT) (4.25-27,5 GHz, 37-43.5 GHz, 45.5-47 GHz, 47.2-48.2 GHz, and 66-71 GHz). It is more than the 17 GHz spectrum, available for the next 5G deployments, where 85% of it is globally aligned.

The European Union has defined a spectrum harmonisation plan for the three first bands concerned for 5G and is leading in 5G band auctions worldwide. By September 2020, commercial 5G service is available in 18 member countries (Figure 13). The 700 MHz band has been assigned in ten of them: Austria, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, and Sweden. Spectrum in the 3.4-3.8 GHz band has been assigned in accordance with 5G technical conditions in 16 countries (13 EU MS and in the UK): Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Portugal, Romania, Luxembourg, Romania, Slovakia, Spain and United Kingdom and the 26 GHz band has been assigned in Italy and in Finland [16].

Figure 13. 5G commercial service availability, September 2020

Latvia, Estonia, and Finland have varied readiness for 5G and spectrum availability (Table 7). All three primary frequencies have already been auctioned in Finland and there is already available commercial service, in Latvia 5G is provided at 3.5 GHz band, but in Estonia 5G is available on existing spectrum and 5G bands will be auctioned in 2021 (Table 8). The country-by-country spectrum availability is detailed in the following sections.

Table 7. 5G strategy and bands follow-up, September 2020

Country	Frequency band	Channel width
Estonia	700MHz	-
	3.4 – 3.8 GHz	-
	26 GHz	-
Finland	700MHz	60 MHz divided to six blocks of 10MHz
	3.4 – 3.8 GHz	390 MHz divided to six blocks of 60 MHz and 70 MHz. In the province of Aland: three blocks of 100MHz
	26 GHz	2.4GHz divided to three blocks of 800MHz
Latvia	700MHz	-
	3.4 – 3.8 GHz	400 MHz divided in eight blocks of 50MHz
	26 GHz	-

Table 8. Spectrum auctions and availability [16]

	700 Mhz	3.5 GHz	26 GHz
Estonia	Auction planned in 2021	Auction planned in 2021	Auction planned in 2021
Finland	Auction: 2016 Available: 2018	Auction: Q3 2018 Available: Q1 2019	Auction: Q2 2020 Available: Q3 2020
Latvia	Auction: Q2 2021 Available: Q3 2022	Auction: Q3 2018 Available: Q1 2019	Under planning

5.1.1.1 Spectrum availability in Latvia

According to the stated objectives, Latvia is set to expand 5G mobile network along land transport corridors and state roads and railways by 2025, covering road transport routes according to the definition of the Trans-European Transport Networks (TEN-T) (Figure 14), as well as urban areas with at least 50,000 inhabitants: Riga, Daugavpils, Liepaja and Jelgava.

Figure 14. Trans-European Transport Network, Latvia

In Latvia 5G network development is carried out at 3.5 GHz frequency, which is divided into 50MHz frequency blocks and available to three MNOs. Available spectrum distribution shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15. 3.5GHz spectrum availability in Latvia

The 700MHz frequency for the development of the 5G network is not available as it is currently used for TV broadcasting. According to the “National Roadmap” for 700 MHz radio spectrum band release in Latvia, it will take place between 1 January 2022 and 30 June 2022. Auction of 700MHz band (703-733 MHz and 758-788 MHz spectrum) will be most likely carried out 2021, with network deployment MNOs starting from 1st of July 2022. 26 GHz will be on offer, however, no exact auction plans and spectrums have been published.

5.1.1.2 Spectrum availability in Estonia

Existing 5G deployment by Telia is carried out on its existing spectrum through the use of Ericsson’s dynamic spectrum sharing technology [17]. Main reason for usage of 2.1 GHz instead of 5G pioneer spectrum are the issues on 3.5 GHz auction suspended in April 2019. 4 licences in 3.5 GHz frequencies initially expected likely in 2021, 700 MHz (703 – 733 MHz, 758 – 788 MHz) and 26 GHz tenders scheduled later in 2021. Despite delays Estonia have a clear aim by to achieve 5G connectivity in major cities and in their peripheral regions by 2023 and transport corridors by 2025. In 5G-ROUTES project scope Telia Estonia have few possible scenarios regarding bands and spectrum used for large scale and localized trials [16]:

- Trial licences for 700 MHz and 3.5 GHz bands;
- Usage of existing bands;
- Commercially available spectrum if auction will be carried out.

5.1.1.3 Spectrum availability in Finland

700 MHz band in Finland was assigned in November 2016, which is paired frequency band: 703 – 733 MHz and 758 - 788 MHz. Band is divided by three MNOs where 10 MHz in lower part and 10 MHz in upper part are available for each of them (Figure 16).

Until the end of 2018, the frequency 3.5 GHz band was used in Finland for fixed wireless access networks, radio amateurs and radio links. The entire 3.5 GHz band was auctioned in September 2018 for the construction of nationwide wireless broadband, with a total of 390 MHz available to three MNOs, a breakdown specified in Figure 17 and Figure 18.

In January 2020, Finland launched a consultation on the 26 GHz auction scheduled in the summer 2020. It included spectrum from 25.1 to 27.5 GHz excluding the lowest 850 MHz part of the 26 GHz band. The auction took place on June 8th, 2020, and the current MNOs - Elisa, Telia and DNA - were each assigned 800 MHz of spectrum. Licences are national for mainland Finland. Elisa won the 25.1-25.9 GHz frequencies, Telia the 25.9-26.7 GHz and DNA got the 26.7-27.5 GHz frequencies (Figure 19). The lowest 850 MHz part of the pioneer band (24.25-25.1 GHz) was reserved for local and/or regional vertical players and research & development or

educational usage. Finland is the second country to have auctioned 26 GHz spectrum at European level and the fourth country at world level. [16]

Figure 16. 700 MHz spectrum availability in Finland

Figure 17. 3.5GHz spectrum availability in Finland [18]

Figure 18. 3.5GHz spectrum availability in Finland (The province of Åland)

Figure 19. 26GHz spectrum availability in Finland

5.1.1.4 Frequency coordination

According to Radio Regulations, in radio region 1 of the International Telecommunications Union (ITU), which includes Latvia and neighbouring countries, the mobile radio service in the radio frequency band 3400-3600 MHz has primary status and the band is also allocated to international mobile telecommunications (IMT). On the other hand, in the 3600-3800 MHz radio frequency band in the ITU Radio 1 region, the mobile radio service has secondary status. Secondary service radio stations shall not cause harmful radio interference to existing or

planned primary service radio stations and shall not require protection of radio stations from harmful radio interference. [19]

Applicable technical conditions and restrictions for the use of the radio frequency band 3400-3800 MHz for mobile and fixed communications networks (MFCN) time duplex (TDD) systems:

Conditions for radio frequency coordination in cross borders between Latvia and neighbouring countries:

Table 9. Frequency coordination in Latvia between neighbouring countries [19]

	3400-3600 MHz	3600-3800 MHz
Border area with Russia	<p>The power flow density generated by THE MFCN station shall not exceed – 154.5 dB (W/(m² × 4 kHz) (or 22,3 dB μ V/m/5 MHz) at the 3 m State border.</p> <p>The calculation shall be based on ITU-R recommendation P.452-16 at 20% of the time, with Smooth Earth terrain profile</p>	<p>Use under protected conditions:</p> <p>The power flow density generated by THE MFCN station shall not exceed – 139,8 dB (W/(m² × 1 MHz) (or 13 dB μ V/m/5 MHz) at the limit of 20 m.</p> <p>The calculation shall be based on ITU-R recommendation P.452-16 at 1% of the time, with Smooth Earth terrain profile.</p> <p>Use under vulnerable conditions *:</p> <p>The power flow density generated by THE MFCN station shall not exceed – 154.5 dB (W/(m² × 4 kHz) (or 22,3 dB μ V/m/5 MHz) at the 3 m State border.</p> <p>The calculation shall be based on ITU-R recommendation P.452-16 at 20% of the time, with Smooth Earth terrain profile.</p> <p>* Secondary service radio stations shall not cause harmful radio interference to existing or planned primary service radio stations and shall not require protection from harmful radio interference from primary service stations. Protection from radio interference caused by other grants is not guaranteed</p>
Border area with Lithuania, Estonia and Belarus	The electromagnetic field value of the MFCN base station shall not exceed 32 dBμV/m/5 MHz at 3 m at the national border.	

	According to ECC Recommendation (15) 01, ITU-R recommendation P.1546-5 at 10% of the time and 50% of the sites shall be used for the calculation.
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As indicated in Table 9, Latvia must comply with very strict rules near Russia border area. Estonia and Finland have the same challenges using the upper part (3600 – 3800 MHz). If better terms than now are not agreed, restrictions on the use of wireless broadband in Finland will be considerable, at worst a few several hundred kilometers from the border. In the lower part (3400-3600 MHz) of the frequency band, the use of frequencies in Finland may be restricted around 100 kilometres from the border.

Trans-national frequency coordination agreements

The use of frequencies in the border area shall be determined by bilateral and trilateral cross-border frequency coordination agreements. Agreements with neighbouring countries are concluded with a view to agreeing the conditions for the use of frequencies in the border area and the principles of frequency coordination, which ensure the use of frequencies without harmful interference from neighbouring countries, as well as facilitate the coordination of frequencies with neighbouring countries. These arrangements shall provide for the level of emission permitted in the direction of the neighbouring countries concerned and for other conditions, and shall specify the cases in which prior coordination of the base stations to be installed with the neighbouring country is to be carried out. In cases where there is no international frequency coordination agreement on conditions for the use of frequencies in the border area, countries shall be guided by the Rules of Procedure of ITU Radio and shall use the relevant CEPT recommendations to address technical issues. [19]

5.2 CAM legislative framework

The European Commission has fully recognised the importance of 5G for future mobility solutions and embraced the deployment of 5G technologies including both network and direct communication in transport as a European public policy priority.

A legislative framework dedicated to the approval of automated vehicles in the EU does not yet exist as it's a complex issue by involving not only automotive and telecoms physical and digital infrastructure, but also communication technologies, and cooperation amongst different eco-systems.

However, existing EU legislation is to a large extent already suitable for the placing on the market of automated and connected vehicles.

There are relevant public policy initiatives that have already been adopted at EU level:

- 1) [The 5G Action Plan for Europe \(5GAP\) \(2016\)](#), calling for action to ensure that the EU can use advanced 5G connectivity as a strategic advantage to lead in digital transformation, in particular, in vertical industries. The action plan set out a clear roadmap for public and private investment on 5G infrastructure in the EU and all main transport paths in all Member States by 2025.
- 2) [The European Strategy on Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems \(C-ITS\) \(2016\)](#) is one of the key EC strategic documents for development of cooperative, connected, and automated mobility. The objective of the C-ITS Strategy is to facilitate the convergence of investments and regulatory frameworks across the EU, to see deployment of mature C-ITS services in 2019 and beyond. C-ITS requires vehicles, traffic signs and motorways to be equipped with technology to send standardized messages to all traffic participants around them. This cooperative element is expected to significantly improve road safety, traffic efficiency and comfort when driving, by helping the driver to make the right decisions and adapt to the traffic situation.

- 3) [The 3rd EU Mobility Package “Europe on the Move” \(2018\)](#) defining an integrated policy to ensure a smooth transition towards a mobility system which is safe, clean and paves the way to connected and automated mobility.
- 4) [The new European Electronic Communications Code \(2018\)](#) - EEC enhances the deployment of 5G networks by ensuring the availability of 5G radio spectrum, provides operators with investment certainty and predictability for at least 20 years in terms of spectrum individual licensing; facilitates the deployment of 5G networks by introducing a light authorization regime for small-area wireless access points, etc.
- 5) [The European Strategy for Data \(2020\)](#), which proposes to set up common data spaces for key sectors: health, the environment, energy, agriculture, mobility and transport, finance, manufacturing, public administration, and skills, as well as a legislative framework on data sharing and governance.
- 6) [The European Green Deal \(2019\)](#) provides a roadmap to turn the EU climate neutral by 2050, by boosting the efficient use of resources by moving to a clean, circular economy and by restoring biodiversity and cut pollution. This includes measures for rolling out cleaner, cheaper, and healthier forms of private and public transport.
- 7) [The European Industrial Strategy \(2020\)](#) aims to deliver on three key priorities: maintaining European industry's global competitiveness and a level playing field, at home and globally, making Europe climate-neutral by 2050 and shaping Europe's digital future. This includes supporting sustainable and smart mobility industries.
- 8) [The Cooperative, Connected, Automated and Autonomous Mobility \(CCAM\) Single Platform](#), first presented in June 2019, aims at advising and supporting the EC in open road testing and making the link to pre-deployment activities. This is done through the coordination of CCAM research, piloting, testing and deployment activities to increase their efficiency and effectiveness as well as integrate existing fora. CCAM also address issues related to data access and exchange, digital and road transport infrastructure, communication technology, cybersecurity, and road safety.
- 9) [5G Strategic Deployment Agenda for Connected and Automated Mobility \(5G SDA\)](#) - The 5G SDA presents a common vision for investing in 5G-ecosystems in the field of Connected and Automated Mobility and identifies the key drivers for accelerating infrastructure roll-out. It will serve as a basis for the upcoming privately as well as publicly supported deployment projects in this field with a particular focus on the upcoming Connecting Europe Facility 2 Digital program.
- 10) [Connecting Europe Facility programme \(CEF2 Digital\) for 2021-2027](#) - aims to support and catalyse investments in digital connectivity for accelerating private investments in 5G infrastructure along highways known as “5G Corridors”, intended to enable Connected and Automated Mobility solutions. The foreseen public funding for the 5G corridors will amount to a significant part of the €2.1 billion finances. This supportive public policy context creates a favourable environment to encourage private investments in large scale deployment of 5G infrastructures, paving the way to future autonomous mobility. The initial goal of CEF Digital is to stimulate investments into a network of pan-European 5G10 Corridors for Connected and Automated Mobility as a first strategic step towards large scale deployment of 5G for CAM and other high value services related to connected vehicles, road operation and overall smart transportation. The estimation for the next five years is - more than 70% of new vehicles and other mobility devices will be exchanging data with external sources, bringing new services and business models to automotive and transportation markets.
- 11) Directive 2007/46/EC, modernised in 2018 (applicable from 1 September 2020), regulates how new vehicles should operate and be designed. Within the EU, mass-produced cars may only be used on public roads if they are type-approved in compliance with the administrative procedures and technical requirements established by the Directive.
- 12) [Guidelines on the exemption procedure for the EU approval of automated vehicles](#) (2019) published by the Technical Committee - Motor vehicles (TCMV) of the European Commission. The goal of these

guidelines is to harmonize the practice of Member States for the national ad-hoc assessment of automated vehicles and to streamline the mutual recognition of such assessment, as well as to ensure fair competition and transparency. The guidelines focus on automated vehicles that can drive themselves in a limited number of driving situations (Levels 3 and 4 of SAE). According to the Guidelines the Member State may grant a provisional approval to the vehicle type, valid only in its territory, provided that it informs the EC and the other Member States thereof without delay by means of a file containing the following elements: (a) the reasons why the technologies or concepts in question make the whole vehicle type incompatible with the requirements; (b) a description of the safety and environmental considerations concerned and the measures taken; (c) a description of the tests, including their results, demonstrating that, by comparison with the requirements from which exemption is sought, at least an equivalent level of safety and environmental protection is ensured. The Commission shall decide by means of an implementing, whether to allow the Member State to grant an EC type-approval in respect of that type of vehicle. Under the Guidelines, the manufacturer shall declare to the type-approval authority the scope of the automated driving mode where and when the automated driving system is designed to operate. This shall include at a minimum: road conditions, geographical area, **environmental** conditions, speed range; other conditions that must be fulfilled for the safe operation in the driving mode.

Figure 20 “Steps towards the development of automated driving in European Union” outlines the overview of EU steps for development of CAM deployments legislation acts within timescale.

STEPS TOWARDS THE DEPLOYMENT OF AUTOMATED DRIVING IN THE EUROPEAN UNION

Figure 20. Steps towards the development of automated driving in European Union

The 5G-PPP Automotive Working Group and the European Commission DG document “5G Strategic Deployment Agenda for Connected and Automated Mobility in Europe” describes the impact of the regulatory environment on innovative business approaches and incentivise investments in mobile network expansion for CAM:

- different network sharing options;
- co-investment approaches;
- spectrum needs harmonization of assignments and reasonable conditions;
- spectrum license duration and other administrative ways to support and ease 5G roll out (e.g. permits authorisation).

The evolution of the cross-border coordination scheme between mobile network operators will ensure improvements in connectivity and eventually - seamless handover between networks at country borders. It will be important to both exploit all possible and appropriate regulatory options and maintain regulatory flexibility to enable CAM and further innovative mobility propositions. In this context, it is anticipated that the CEF programme will offer concrete opportunities to test, in a "sand box " scenario environment, new regulatory approaches supported by the modernised telecom rules. A consideration of the regulatory environment is compliance with competition rules when CEF funding will be used.

With CEF funding, the different models and supporting arrangements need to be consistent with competition principles to avoid devaluing or crowding-out private investments.

When the particular use of CEF funding is being considered, cooperation arrangements involving at least two or more undertakings from the same or different sectors may have to be set-up according to specific models, regarding the sharing of passive and active infrastructure network elements, in so far as they may have implications on the level of investments required to deploy. Moreover, the project may involve different funding mechanisms and financial instruments, including resources from the Member States. There is the need to identify criteria to ensure consistency with EU competition law principles applied to CEF-funded projects, especially with respect to antitrust and state-aid rules.

5.2.1 Latvia CAM Legislation

Recently the Ministry of Transport of the Republic of Latvia has developed “Transport development guidelines for 2021-2027”, what determines the following CAM directions related to 5G-ROUTES project objectives:

- 1) Provision of multimodal public transport (e.g. mobility points);
- 2) ITS use and digitization opportunities - 5G along VIA Baltica and RailBaltica;
- 3) Continuation of implementation of the Rail Baltica project (incl. design of regional stations);
- 4) Continuation of provision of national main roads (TEN-T network) and regional roads (Regional accessibility);
- 5) Development and implementation of a micro-mobility development plan.

In the beginning of 2018 Latvian stakeholders of transport industry have elaborated “Guidelines on Testing Automated Vehicle Technologies”, what was adopted by the Ministry of Transport. The Guidelines set out requirements for testing automated vehicles on publicly accessible roads in Latvia, thus reducing the potential risks associated with the participation of such vehicles in traffic.

Within Interreg BSR programme’s project [Sohjoa Baltic](#) a study “Research of Legal Regulatory Changes for Testing and Implementing Automated Vehicles and Their Technology” was occurred. Work is currently under way to identify the exact routes in Aizkraukle and Jelgava cities, where a pilot project launching an automated bus could be carried out [30].

According to “The Roadmap to Automated Electric Shuttles in Public Transport - The Legal Framework Testing” developed by IKEM – Institut für Klimaschutz, Energie und Mobilität e.V. within [BSR Sohjoa Baltic project](#), automotive vehicle technology does not require special authorisation if vehicle control can be assumed at any time by a trained and licensed test driver or driver and operator. In accordance with the Guidelines for Test Vehicles, vehicles must be:

- suitable for participation in traffic, compliant with all vehicle requirements, and used in traffic in a manner that does not violate the requirements of regulatory enactments governing traffic;
- equipped with a manual control mode;
- shown to have successfully performed testing on closed test routes or in test areas;
- the legal entity responsible for automated vehicle testing must have adequate insurance coverage.

The driver must be in possession of a valid driving license for the relevant category, corresponding to the vehicle type. The test driver and test vehicle operator must have at least five years of experience as a driver in the appropriate category. The driver and operator of the test vehicle must also submit information to the legal entity organizing the test, and their driving history must indicate that they do not pose a particular risk to other road users.

Standards for the vehicle operator and vehicle driving: During the testing of automated vehicles on public roads, the vehicle must be monitored at all times by an appropriately trained and licensed test driver or test vehicle driver and test vehicle operator who can assume control of the vehicle as necessary.

The guidelines set out a series of obligations regarding the competence of the test driver and test operator, including comprehensive knowledge of the technologies used in testing, as well as the capabilities and limitations of these technologies; knowledge of the test vehicle; and recognition of the situations in which it may be necessary to interfere in vehicle operation. Under the guidelines, the legal entity organizing the test must establish rules for the test driver and the behaviour of the operator of test vehicle and ensure that they are known by and understandable to test vehicle drivers and to the test vehicle operators; it must also ensure that the test driver and test vehicle operator are competent and have received proper training. The training of the test driver and the test vehicle operator should include practice in analyzing potentially hazardous traffic situations and taking appropriate action to assume control of the vehicle. In the training process, attention should be paid to the transition from traditional manual to automatic control [20].

5.2.2 Estonia CAM legislation

In Estonia, automated vehicles (SAE levels 0–3) can be tested in road traffic using a test plate certificate.

- These vehicles must have a driver, either within the vehicle or acting remotely, who is responsible for the vehicle and takes control of it if necessary.
- Testing can take place on public roads or off-road.
- The Road Administration can issue a testing permit for six months with the possibility of an extension.
- The Road Administration requires manufacturers to follow the EU Directive 2007/46 at least in its most important parts, e.g. with regard to seat installation, safety windows, break acceleration, door closing-force, emergency lights, reflectors, light installation and use in car traffic, and bus ‘kill switches’.

There are no specific requirements for automated vehicles. A driver is legally responsible for following traffic rules and for ensuring that the vehicle’s technical functions are maintained.

5.2.3 Finland CAM Legislation

Under national law, every vehicle must have a responsible driver, but in tests of automated vehicles, the driver can be either inside or outside the vehicle (like the situation in Denmark and Sweden). The term driver does not have a legal definition in Finnish law.

In Finland, testing of automated vehicles (SAE levels 0–5) is possible in road traffic using a test plate certificate.

Finland's technology-friendly licensing practice allows autonomous vehicles to be tested on public roads provided that a permit has been issued by the Finnish Transport and Communications Agency Traficom. Traficom grants test plate certificates based on an application by a testing organisation.

Test plate certificate entitle the bearer to drive test vehicles, to a limited extent and on a temporary basis, both in road traffic and off road, under the conditions detailed in the test plate certificate.. A Trade Register extract from the company's country of incorporation not more than three months old must be appended to the application. Non-Finnish based organisations need to apply for a Business ID with the Trade Register to get a Finnish traffic insurance for 3rd party liability.

The applicant must also enclose a trial plan that includes:

- a general description of the trials,
- technical specifications of the test vehicles,
- information on the road area where the trials are to be conducted,
- proof of insurance cover for third-party liability, and
- a description of measures to ensure road safety, including cybersecurity and privacy handling.

The draft plan has to be sent to Traficom, and, dependent on the feedback, Traficom will provide the permission for an online application. The test permit is normally valid for 1 year, valid for the use mentioned in the trial plan, and includes obligations for (free-format) reporting, and can be renewed automatically.

5.3 Investment plans & models

5.3.1 European Commission Study on CEF – Cost of deployment of 5G corridor

According to the interim finding of a study conducted by a team of independent consultants for the EC to support the implementation of CEF Digital [31], these four scenarios will be considered in 5G-ROUTES project:

- 1. Minimum scenario:** a scenario based on the critical data that should be transmitted in any traffic conditions. The reference is the minimum bitrates observed on the current tests. Use cases that require additional services, such as the video visualization to improve driver comfort and to reassure him, are not considered as critical services during the busy hour (busy hour: the worst traffic conditions meaning almost 200 vehicles per km on highway). However, they will be available in more flexible traffic conditions. Under this scenario (equipment every 4km), the total investment required to cover the 26,000km CEF2 corridors will be €800m with a price of €12,000/km for fibre, a price of €1700/km for V2I and a price of €17,000/km for V2N. This would represent a total of €31,000/km.
- 2. Classic scenario:** a scenario based on the critical data that should be transmitted in any traffic conditions. The reference is the average bitrates observed on the current tests with the possibility to have main use cases at the same time (the majority are not always-on). Under this scenario (equipment every 3km), the total investment required will be €988m with a price of €12,000/km for fibre, a price of €1700/km for V2I and a price of €24,000/km for V2N. This would represent a total of €38,000/km.

3. **Breaking scenario:** a scenario based on all 5G CAM use cases, including those that are more specifically designed for the driver (and not for the unmanned algorithm) or those that are designed for the V2V communication, V2N2V as a fallback. It also considers future services that will require higher bitrates and have not been tested yet. With this scenario (equipment every 1 km, bitrate of 30 Mbps), the total investment required will be €2,578m with a price of €19,000/km for fibre, a price of €10,000/km for V2I and a price of €70,000/km for V2N. This would represent a total of €99,000/km.
4. **Future Proof scenario:** in this scenario, the network will support any conceivable future service, (equipment every 0.4 km, bitrate of 100 Mbps), the total investment required will be €5,460m with a price of €19,000/km for fibre, a price of €10,000/km for V2I and a price of €181,000/km for V2N. This would represent a total of €210,000/km.

		MINIMUM 5G Scenario	CLASSIC 5G Scenario	BREAKING 5G Scenario	FUTURE PROOF 5G Scenario
BACKHAUL NETWORK	Existing Backhaul along 5G corridors	50% available		20% available	
	k€/km	12	12	19	19
	m€	314	314	500	500
5G CELLULAR NETWORK	CAM use case	1 Mbps Guaranteed bitrate <i>in highly traffic period</i>	2 Mbps Guaranteed bitrate <i>in highly traffic period</i>	30 Mbps Average bitrate <i>normal conditions</i>	100 Mbps Average bitrate <i>normal conditions</i>
	Available Frequencies	700Mhz & 3500Mhz, 260Mhz nationwide BW			
	Business Model	Multi-operators & Active Ran Sharing		Standalone & Passive Ran Sharing	
	Inter-site distance evaluated	≈4 km	≈3 km	≈1 km	≈0,4 km
	Site cost (& installation)	90k€			
	5G corridor dist.	26 000 km			
	Existing radio sites	1 every 10 km			
	5G site upgrade	40 k€			
	k€/km	17	24	70	181
	m€	443	631	1 818	4 700
	TOTAL 5G V2N COSTS		757	945	2 318
V2I INFRA	RoadSide Unit cost (& installation)	5 k€		20 k€	
	Distance between two RSU	3 km		2 km	
	5G corridor dist.	26 000 km			
	k€/km	1,7	1,7	10	10
	m€	43	43	260	260
TOTAL V2I & V2N COSTS		800	988	2 578	5 460

Figure 21. Deployment costs estimation for 4 scenarios

The figures in the table above only represent a first and generalised indication which will vary across member states and regions (e.g. cost for civil works) and significantly depend on the specific topography and the availability/reusability of legacy mobile network infrastructure, i.e. existing 2G/3G/3G/4G sites of mobile network operators and the various network grid structures deployed so far. A refined model has to reflect that the requirements for ITS and CAM services have to take into account that the 5G corridors and each corridors sections have different numbers of vehicles on average and during rush hours, which could be grouped into

traffic demand scenarios. This will lead to a more differentiated model for addressing the traffic demand (physical and digital) by 5G network deployments without significant overprovisioning and associated costs.

5.3.2 Business models for cross-border environment

Possible business models from for cross border environment described below referred from 5G PPP Automotive Working Group material “Business Feasibility Study for 5G V2X Deployment” (2019) [32].

The building blocks of 5G-enabled CCAM solutions in cross-border environments integrate multiple telecommunication and computing technologies. From a business point of view, these elements are developed and/or managed by different stakeholders that will participate in the value chain (e.g., Automotive Suppliers, Telecom Equipment vendors OEMs, MNOs). New roles and business opportunities will be identified for different Use Cases and cross border scenarios. **Use Cases are some of the main drivers for the development of business models, business cases, value chains, and strategic decisions.**

In a cross-border environment, new relations between market players will be established. For instance, new services definition and how connectivity can affect them by enhancing or enabling them for deployment. Business model examples, where the evolution from a linear value chain to a multi-linear relationship model might be expected. New neutral operators for dedicated AD and network functions (e.g. MEC service, RAN sharing, ToD) may arise, as well as adaptation of accounting and payment models in an inter-operator environment for mixed markets and different use cases.

The cost of deployment of the 5G technology to be used in any CCAM use case shall be divided in three fractions:

1. Cost of 5G network deployment (Capital Expenditure - CAPEX)
2. Cost of HW and SW for the embedded telco system in the cars (CAPEX)
3. System operation (Operational Expenditure - OPEX)

The adoption of new business models for CCAM will help to identify appropriate financing schemes for 5G-enabled transportation solutions, revenue allocation and procurement models.

5.3.3 Infrastructure and network sharing models

The cost of deploying and operating 5G V2X for providing CAM and other Intelligent Transport System (ITS) services will be very high and challenging to be carried by one single network provider, e.g., a single MNO or Road Infrastructure Operator.

Four different network sharing models are described [32], according to the level of sharing of network infrastructure, network functionalities and radio spectrum between different network operators. A possible scenario is sharing more extensively at an earlier phase, followed by independent and separate investments by each operator. These models will co-exist and be used according to the area and users’ density. Different sharing models have significant implications on the required investments to deploy and operate 5G V2X networks and the savings in CAPEX and OPEX with regards to the baseline of no sharing based on the estimates provided by:

- 1) Passive infrastructure sharing: each network operator deploys its own network in the service area. Only passive infrastructure elements are shared between operators, e.g. space, masts, power generators, and air conditioning equipment. These elements could be deployed by Road Infrastructure Operators, a joint MNOs venture or third-party infrastructure providers. Savings: 16% to 35% CAPEX and 16% to 35% OPEX;

- 2) Active infrastructure sharing excluding spectrum sharing: active elements of the cellular network such as base stations are shared. Each operator is still transmitting on his own spectrum. Savings: 33% to 35% CAPEX and 25% to 33% OPEX;
- 3) Active infrastructure sharing including spectrum sharing: active elements such as base stations are shared. One single operator operates the dedicated spectrum. The RAN connects to the core network of the visitor's operator (the different MNOs) directly. Savings: 33% to 45% CAPEX and 30% to 33% OPEX.
- 4) Core network sharing: elements of the core network are shared by more than one network operator. Savings: the savings corresponding to just sharing elements of the core network are reported as very low. If the sharing agreement includes some aspects of the RAN, then the savings are similar to active infrastructure sharing including spectrum sharing model.

National roaming can be considered a form of active sharing. In this way subscribers can roam to other networks within a country (e.g., in case coverage is provided by an exclusive operator in a locality). As in the general international roaming case, the connection goes to the core network of the exclusive operator before going to the core network of the visitor's operator; this is referred to as Home Routing and it could generate additional delays if used as the default roaming option. Other alternatives, such as Local Breakout should be considered for latency-sensitive services. In addition, international roaming should be supported especially for cross border corridors.

Any type of sharing will require a certain set of agreements between network operators, related to the passive sharing (also on a lease base), active sharing involving a joint deployment, agreements of using other network operator's network for a specific technology (e.g. 2G) or sharing agreements related to specific locations. Moreover, they need to be in line with the regulatory frameworks in each country. This implies both telecom regulation and any possible concerns from the competition authorities.

Additionally, backhauling options and other possible sharing models are envisaged. While certain areas already count with optical fibre backhaul deployed along roads, commercial agreements are sometimes unfeasible to allow sharing mechanisms for such fibre access. In any case, sharing options should be encouraged to reduce additional deployment costs; for example, if a road operator owns fibre backhaul infrastructure, it could collaborate with MNO(s) to cover different geographical segment.

5.3.4 Charging and revenue models

The revenue models for the 5G V2X deployment are highly dependent on revenues generated on the application level. At 5G PPP Automotive Working Group study "Business Feasibility Study for 5G V2X Deployment" [32], "pay per use" model is considered to estimate the network revenues. In pay per use, it is considered that a fee is paid every time a section of a road is used (like toll fees on highways). Other options include one-time payment; in this case, it is assumed that users pay an intermediary up-front fee that guarantees service subscription. Recurring subscription (with fair-use policy) is also an important and likely model.

The monetization from the network is highly dependent on the services enabled by connectivity. For example, in-vehicle applications focus on infotainment (e.g., audio/video streaming). However, they are expected to cover, through virtualization and artificial intelligence, other use cases requiring isolated software execution environments and secure interaction between applications and vehicle's smart devices, sensors, and actuators. Such approach facilitates creation of new business opportunities for municipalities, insurances, and other service providers, as well as road and connectivity infrastructure owners.

Ideas for business setup

To make a deployment evaluation, the following assumptions are made:

- The network deployment investment is done by one actor. For example, this actor will be a network operator (it could be a traditional MNO or potentially any actor, such as a road operator, willing to invest in network deployment).
- The network operator might have the possibility to reuse physical infrastructure (such as towers, power supply or fibre network) from a road infrastructure provider.
- CAM services might be provided by road operators, OEMs, MNOs, or other service provider to have this role. It is not necessarily the same actor in charge of the network deployment and operation.
- The CAM service provider receives a fee from end customers. It could also be envisaged that service fees are indirectly covered by OEMs in their service offers to end customers.
- The CAM service provider will then pay a fee to network operators for the provision of connectivity products and added-value services. This is the main revenue source considered in the analysis. The Figure 22 describes a potential business scenario. Also, other business setups are feasible depending on the market conditions and the regional or national interests, as well as regulatory frameworks in the country.

Figure 22. Main business setup for the network operator deployment analysis

5.3.5 EU funds and investments in Latvia

Latvia has made progress on the goals of the national broadband strategy for 2013-2020, which include the Digital Agenda for Europe targets and the Gigabit Society objectives. Latvia has been among the EU frontrunners on fibre and 4G deployment. It has the highest fibre to the premises (FTTP) coverage in the EU in rural areas (69%) and being well above the EU's average by the next generation access (NGA) coverage in the whole country (91%).

The main objective of the broadband strategy was to reduce the digital divide between urban and rural areas. Bridging the digital divide remains a challenge, despite the progress ensured by EU-funded projects. Some progress in coverage has been made through the 'middle-mile project' financed from EU structural funds to

deploy optical cables and optical network access points in places that currently have no broadband access and no plans for commercial deployment. At every access point, operators have the opportunity to create a local loop (the 'last mile') utilising the new network to offer retail services to end users. 'Last mile' investments by companies are, however, lacking in some parts of the country. Further efforts are necessary to close the last mile gap. The middle mile project is critically important to the development and stability of the last mile networks. However, low income and population scarcity in rural areas cause low commercial interest for deployment of the last mile. Latvia is making further efforts to reach territories not covered by the current State aid programme and to bring the middle mile as close to end-users as possible. This will make deployment of the last mile more economically attractive for electronic communication operators. The middle mile and last mile development measures, including State aid, will be evaluated and included in the broadband plan for 2021-2027.

The national **5G Roadmap in Latvia** was approved by the Cabinet of Ministers in February 2020. Four objectives were defined within implementation of 5G Roadmap in Latvia:

1) Timely harmonization of radio spectrum bands for use in the provision of 5G mobile networks.

Since 2019 the 3.4-3.8 GHz band has been awarded for 5G mobile communication. The 700 MHz band is currently used for TV broadcasting - digital terrestrial television (DTT) by Tet whose rights of use expire in 31 December 2021. The use of the 700 MHz band for wireless broadband is planned for 2022, with auctions expected between end 2020 and mid-2021. Advances in allocating this band depend on the DTT migration and the frequency coordination (to avoid mutual interferences) with Russia and Belarus. 703-733 MHz / 758-788 MHz bands will be allocated for wireless broadband services and could be used for Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR) system based on agreement of PPDR system owner and electronic service providers. Allocation of 733-736 MHz un 788-791 MHz bands for Internet of Things (IoT) will be subject to consider in the next sector policy plan making period. Until the end of 2020 a part of 26 GHz spectrum band will be allocated for the use of mobile communication services. While spectrum bands above 24 GHz are already used for 5G tests, realizing the allocation of substantive frequency resources between 24.25 GHz and 27.5 GHz for 5G still requires coordination with the military. Latvia is one of the frontrunners in preparation for the deployment of 5G, ranking 5th on the 5G readiness indicator, with 33% of 5G spectrum assigned.

2) At least one large city must be selected in each EU Member State, where 5G availability must be ensured by the end of 2020;

Using radio spectrum of 3.5 GHz and higher to provide "last mile", 5G mobile network base stations may be required every 350 m in urban streets and every 500 m outside urban roads. Consequently, the planning of 5G networks is different and more complex than the planning of 3G or 4G networks.

3) By 2025 continuous 5G coverage must be ensured in all major cities (in Latvia - i.e. Riga, Daugavpils, Jelgava and Liepaja);

Currently commercial 5G services are available in the two cities in Latvia: Jelgava and Daugavpils. It is important to develop the construction of a 5G mobile communication network in those municipalities whose territory is crossed by TEN-T roads or where a TEN-T port or airport hub is located in the vicinity of an urban area.

4) By 2025 the availability of 5G must be ensured along all main land transport routes, including the nodes of Latvian ports and airports (i.e. Daugavpils, Liepāja, Rīga, Ventspils).

The Baltic States envisage the gradual implementation of 5G networks on the Via Baltica to improve the interoperability of connected vehicles, as well as to connect the Baltic States with other important European transport corridors. An important element of the commitment is to ensure cross-border cooperation so that the systems set up operate without restrictions, both in border areas and throughout the transport corridor. The

vehicles will mainly use 5G networks for mutual data transmission and communication with the surrounding infrastructure, as well as for the collection of data from different types of infrastructure sensors for further processing.

Particularly, 5G-ROUTES WP3 and WP4 tasks through the Use Cases and cross-border trials, where project partners: TELIA, Eriksson, LMT, EDI, PV role is essential, will provide contribution in 5G Roadmap implementation at European level.

EU Projects in Latvia:

During 2014-2020 Latvian beneficiaries participate in 11 Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) projects in the field of transport and receive €283.6 million in CEF Transport co-funding, (out of which €270.4 million come from the Cohesion envelope), with investments in these projects of €355.1 million [29].

Additionally 3 projects are located in Latvia but without the involvement of Latvian beneficiaries. These projects correspond to a total of €74.1 million of CEF Transport funding and a total investment of €354.9 million.

Figure 23. Overview of CEF funding in Latvia 2014-2020

1) 5G infrastructure and Via Baltic gateway

In September 2018 Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania signed a memorandum of understanding where they agree to cooperate on the deployment of the 4G+, 4G ++ and 5G network along a section of the Via Baltica: Tallinn (Estonia) – Riga (Latvia) – Kaunas (Lithuania) – Lithuanian/Polish border in order improve road safety, to foster sustainable mobility and innovation in transportation systems and test autonomous vehicles. The Memorandum of Understanding was signed on 28 Sept. 2018 in Riga at the 5G Techritory event. Although focused on C-V2X, elements of the Riga-Tallinn segment builds upon Smart E67 project (ITS).

In September 2020 Latvia, Lithuania, Estonia and Poland have signed a memorandum for cooperation in introducing 5G and Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) solutions. The signed memorandum approved a roadmap for the construction of 5G and CAM corridors along the Via Baltica transport thoroughfare connecting the four countries. The 5G network is an important stimulant for innovative transport solutions and the improvement of traffic safety in the North Sea-Baltic Sea transport corridor.

In line with the EU's targets for the availability of 5G along major land transport routes, the right to use the 700 MHz spectrum band will include a condition for the provision of 5G coverage along major land transport (TEN-T) roads. Baltic expert working groups are working on the issue of providing the Via Baltica (E67) road with passive broadband infrastructure to create the preconditions for 5G connectivity along the entire road have identified the location of existing fiber optic cable networks along the international route the Latvian section of the Via Baltica (E67) motorway, while also identifying the availability of electricity infrastructure and the coverage of mobile base stations. Based on the identified information, preparations are underway for the project implementation.

2) Rail Baltic project

The Rail Baltic project is the largest Baltic-region infrastructure project financed by EU CEF programme with a goal to integrate the Baltic States in the European rail network. The project includes five European Union countries – Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia and indirectly also Finland. It will connect Helsinki, Tallinn, Pärnu, Riga, Panevežys, Kaunas, Vilnius, Warsaw. The Baltic part of the Rail Baltica project is referred to as the Rail Baltica Global Project. Rail Baltic is the part of the EU's North Sea Baltic TEN-T corridor with length of 870km, max. speed: 249 km/h (passengers), 120 km/h (freight), environmentally friendly – powered by electricity, produces less noise and vibration and will be equipped with 5G technologies.

The total estimated cost of the rail Baltic project is 5.8 billion euro in all three countries and EU financing is projected at 85%. In December 2020 Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA) and joint venture of the Baltic States RB Rail AS signed two additional cross-border Grant Agreements on the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) funding for Rail Baltica. The total budget of these two Agreements is 214,3 million euros, of which the CEF contribution will be of a maximum amount of 182,2 million, constituting 85% of the total eligible costs. This additional CEF funding will enable the project to further advance construction works in the key passenger terminals in Estonia and Latvia and ensure the construction of further main line section from Kaunas towards the Lithuanian – Latvian state border. Furthermore, the additional CEF funding will allow to progress with the development of the key railway subsystems, planning and design of regional stations and infrastructure maintenance facilities for all three Baltic States.

During 2020 the main performed Rail Baltic activities in Latvia were: i) RIX construction (II phase), ii) Riga central Station construction (II phase), iii) Riga main line construction, iv) Salaspils intermodal freight terminal technical design regional stations design and v) land acquisition (II phase).

3) Construction of Kekava's bypass

The construction of Kekava's bypass (part of Via Baltic project) is the first the public-private partnership (PPP) project, implemented by "Latvian State Roads" and scheduled to begin in the second quarter of 2021. The estimated total budget for 20 years period would be ~270 million EUR. The state will pay ~13,5 mill EUR per year to road builders.

National mobility and 5G policy and EU Funding in Latvia in 2021-2027:

In December of 2020, the Ministry of Transport of the Republic of Latvia has developed "Transport Development Guidelines for 2021-2027", what determines the following three strategic directions related to 5G and CAM deployment:

- 1) Establishment of a multimodal public transport network with rail as the "backbone" of public transport, integrating Rail Baltica into the existing state and municipal transport network, creating multimodal transport and passenger transfer hubs, enhancement of population mobility, development of safe roads and street infrastructure etc.;
- 2) Improved international connectivity by implementing the Rail Baltica project (including Riga International Airport as the part of RB project), making Riga an important and modern multimodal transport hub, incl. upgraded infrastructure required for mobility development;
- 3) Establishment of broadband electronic communications network in line with EU connectivity objectives by developing the infrastructure needed for the "middle mile" and "last mile" electronic communications networks and broadband mapping.

Meanwhile "Transport development guidelines for 2021-2027" foreseen EU funds and national investments for:

- 1) Availability of 5G mobile communication infrastructure coverage along the VIA Baltica and Rail Baltica transport corridors - 202,5 km for Via Baltica and 265 km for Rail Baltica;
- 2) Design and construction of Rail Baltica regional stations by integrating the railway line Rail Baltica into the existing national and municipal public transport route network;
- 3) Continue the implementation of the Rail Baltica project, at the same time developing Riga metropolitan area as the multimodal transport hub integrated in the TEN-T network, reorganization of urban transport and public infrastructure.

Various EU financial support instruments will be available for the implementation of 5G and mobility in Latvia during 2021-2027 period:

- 1) **Cohesion Funding** - the priority investment area and implementation of the Cohesion Policy 2021-2027 is the focus on Policy Objective 3: a more connected Europe – Mobility and regional information and communications technology connectivity. The transport infrastructure in Latvia remains far below the EU average standards in terms of the network's coverage, carbon emissions and safety issues, with significant regional accessibility issues. High priority investment needs have therefore been identified to develop a sustainable, climate resilient, intelligent, secure and intermodal Trans-European Transport Networks and their accessibility, in particular to:
 - bring national sections of the Trans-European Transport Networks road core and comprehensive network to meet EU standards, including safety;
 - complete the Trans-European Transport Networks conventional rail core network;
 - improve access to the Trans-European Transport Networks and cross border mobility.

Levels of traffic congestion in larger Latvian cities remain an issue due to the limited coordination of investments with policies for urban transport. Priority investment needs have therefore been identified to promote sustainable multimodal urban mobility, in particular to:

- develop urban transport systems within relevant integrated territorial development strategies and sustainable urban mobility plans, with a focus on functional areas.

There is a significant digital divide, in terms of broadband infrastructure and communication coverage between urban and rural areas in Latvia, even though the country performs relatively well in terms of overall broadband connectivity. The investment needs have therefore been identified to enhance digital connectivity, in particular to:

- deploy very-high capacity networks, eliminating coverage gaps in rural and less populated areas;
 - improve the cybersecurity and physical security of public very high capacity networks investments.
- 2) **European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)** - for research and technological development, development of local, regional transport, telecommunications and energy networks and related infrastructure;
 - 3) **Connecting Europe Facility (CEF)** – around 3-billion-euro EU funds are foreseen for the establishment of digital infrastructure and the introduction of 5G technologies. EU co-financing rates for projects will be up to 50%, if the projects actions are with important cross-border dimension, such as continuous coverage of 5G technologies on major transport corridors or for the deployment of core networks between EU Member States and between the EU and third countries. For the projects actions implementing gigabit connectivity of socio-economic drivers EU co-financing will be even up to 75%. Within CEF EC plans to introduce a new sub-programme 5G4EU initiative for municipal-initiated projects to provide 5G services in places, where there are no plans to deploy 5G in the coming years.
 - 4) **InvestEU** - investments in sustainable infrastructure, including digital connectivity.
 - 5) **Connecting Europe Broadband Fund (CEBF)** - priority is broadband projects (technology-neutral using high-performance technologies; incl. 5G) in sparsely populated and rural areas in areas that meet the criteria of the EU guidelines for "white" and "grey" areas.
 - 6) **Horizon Europe programme** – EU research & innovation investment programme 2021-2027 with budget 95.5 billion euro. Horizon Europe will incorporate five research and innovation missions to increase the effectiveness of funding by pursuing clearly defined targets: a) Adaptation to climate change including societal transformation; b) Cancer; c) Climate-neutral and smart cities; d) Healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters; e) Soil health and food.

All above indicated EU financial instruments for 2021-2027 are still under development and conditions will be clarified during the decision-making process and approval by EC and responsible national authorities.

5.3.6 EU funds and investments in Estonia

In 2014, Estonia updated its targets and measures for broadband as part of its Digital Agenda 2020. The strategy envisioned full coverage with connections of at least 30 Mbps by 2020. It also aimed at promoting the take-up of ultra-fast subscriptions (> 100 Mbps for 60% or more of all internet subscriptions by 2020). Deployment of a middle-mile network of fibre-optic cables is ongoing in Estonia, resulting on 98% of all residential buildings, companies, and public authorities located within 1.5 km of at least one fibre-optic network access point. The goal of Estonia with its 5G roadmap is to achieve 5G connectivity in major cities by 2023 and along transport corridors by 2025.

The main goals for broadband development are: 1) the completion of the high-speed middle-mile network, 2) the expansion of the broadband access network in regions of market failure (reducing administrative burden

related to the construction of a communication network by simplifying the relevant legal framework; obligatory installation of “last mile” connections in new buildings which are part of state-funded development projects; promoting community initiatives for the development of fast internet connections; supporting the construction of “last mile” connections in areas of market failure, including rural areas, if necessary), 3) the analysis of the need for external connections and implementing relevant projects when necessary; 4) ensuring the availability of radio frequencies that meet the requirements of information society to provide internet access for end users in areas where fixed networks are not available; 5) the promotion of the principle of network neutrality, which means that electronic communication operators may not restrict final users’ access to legal communication services, websites or available platforms; 6) the promotion of secure public WiFi networks, mainly provided by (local) public sector organisations.

An important mechanism is the “Estonian Wideband Infrastructure Network” project, EstWin, which seeks to solve the rural connectivity challenge in an area underserved by telecom operators. EstWin aims to bring ultra-fast internet access within 1,5 km of all rural households, enterprises and institutions in the project area. Funded almost 100% by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), this project was a finalist in the European Broadband Awards.

Estonian 5G Roadmap:

Estonia aims to develop 5G connectivity in a form that would allow data free movement, the development of innovative services and the introduction of artificial intelligence. Estonia aims to achieve 5G connectivity in larger cities and in their periphery by 2023 and in the transport corridors by 2025. The roadmap does not create barriers to small cellular wireless access points commissioning and use. It ensures that telecommunications companies have the widest possible right of access to natural persons infrastructure controlled by national or local authorities. It identifies bottlenecks in information exchange and deal with a single information point, developing user-friendliness. It identifies the need for investments in the fiber optic base network and base stations to switch to 5G. It agrees and develop roles between the private and public sectors private and public investment model. Estonia aims to monitor and map the geographical map of 5G deployment (www.netikaart.ee). The Roadmap looks for opportunities to work with neighbouring countries and at the European level to create joint investment plans for cross-border 5G infrastructure, such as 5G corridors for interconnected and automated mobility. Estonia will start a CAD project on the Via Baltica corridor and cooperate with border countries. It will look for 5G synergies in the Rail Baltic project. If necessary, it will support pilot projects. It looks for opportunities for Smart City 5G tests. In the spring of 2019, a competition for 3400-3800 MHz frequency licenses was announced. In the first half of 2020, a competition was announced for 694-790 MHz frequency licenses. A public consultation was conducted in the 24.25-27.5 GHz band to identify market expectations for its introduction. The consultation deadline was end of 2019. The possible use of the 40.5-43.5 GHz and 66-71 GHz frequency bands is specified.

EU Projects in Estonia:

EU projects can be organized in 3 directions: i) infrastructure ii) telecommunications/services iii) research and analyses.

1) Infrastructure projects:

- a) **5G infrastructure and Via Baltic gateway:** In terms of regional co-ordination, in September 2018, Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania signed a memorandum of understanding where they agree to cooperate on the deployment of the 4G+, 4G ++ and 5G network along a section of the Via Baltica: Tallinn (Estonia) – Riga (Latvia) – Kaunas (Lithuania) – Lithuanian/Polish border in order improve road safety, to foster sustainable mobility and innovation in transportation systems and test autonomous vehicles. The Memorandum of Understanding was signed on 28 Sept. 2018 in Riga at the 5G

Techritory event. Although focused on C-V2X, elements of the Riga-Tallinn segment builds upon Smart E67 project (ITS).

- b) **Rail Baltic project:** The Rail Baltic project is the largest Baltic-region infrastructure project financed by EU CEF programme with a goal to integrate the Baltic States in the European rail network. The project includes five European Union countries – Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia and indirectly also Finland. It will connect Helsinki, Tallinn, Pärnu, Riga, Panevežys, Kaunas, Vilnius, Warsaw. The Baltic part of the Rail Baltica project is referred to as the Rail Baltica Global Project. Rail Baltic is the part of the EU’s North Sea Baltic TEN-T corridor with length of 870km, max. speed: 249 km/h (passengers), 120 km/h (freight), environmentally friendly – powered by electricity, produces less noise and vibration and will be equipped with 5G technologies.

2) Telecommunications / services projects:

- a) **X-ROAD:** X-Road is a "centrally managed distributed Data Exchange Layer between information systems". Organizations can exchange information over the Internet using X-Road to ensure confidentiality, integrity and interoperability between data exchange parties. Nearly 1 billion queries are managed through this infrastructure and 52 thousand organizations are indirectly serving users through this platform.
- b) **5G service use case study (Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications (70003158), Reference number :224830):** Estonia needs a leap forward in connectivity, and 5G technologies provide an opportunity for this. We need to know how Estonian companies and people can benefit from global 5G trends and the state, together with companies, support structural changes in key areas of 5G content and business services (e.g. digital culture, industrial digitization, energy, environment and road safety). The study is necessary for a more substantive preparation of the planning of Estonian cohesion policy 2021-2027 funds. As an important result of the study, we want 5G usage stories mapped in the Estonian context. We want usage case descriptions in areas of greater public impact, where there is a clear perspective to support the development of the field, which requires describing 5G usage stories now and in the foreseeable future and clearly identifying those responsible, parties and possible activities.

3) Research and analyses projects:

- a) **5G structural funds: “Tallinn University of Technology Development Program 2016-2022, code 2014-2020.4.01.16-0032”):** Part of the structural funds at Tallinn University of Technology, also address the need to meet the emerging communication technologies such as 4G, 5G, IoT etc. Number of professorship funding’s are on-going filling the gaps of research and development jointly with local industry (e.g., mobile networks operator).
- b) **European Research Area Chair (ERA Chair) projects:** These are large scale support and action measures supporting to alleviate the research and development productivity. Cognitive Electronics (COEL) ERA chair project established at Tallinn University of Technology created new synergies among other instruments to support sustainability.

5.3.7 EU funds and investments in Finland

In order to remain at the forefront of technological and digital service development, the Finnish government issued a Digital Infrastructure Strategy 2025 [36]. The digital infrastructure strategy specifies Finland's technology-neutral broadband objectives for 2025 and the means by which they will be achieved. The needs of both business and consumers have been taken into consideration in the strategy. The strategy contains measures for promoting the implementation of 5G and supporting optical fibre construction. The strategy also identifies key challenges facing the digitalisation of services and existing infrastructure as well as data needs, which are

crucial to, for example, automated transportation. The strategy is in line with global development trends, such as augmented reality, the Internet of Things, automation, artificial intelligence and M2M communication. High-quality and reliable communications networks pave the way for these services and new innovations. The measures proposed in the strategy involve, among other things, the construction of 5G networks and frequency policy, streamlining network permit and construction procedures, promoting market functionality, and supporting research and innovation. At the end of 2020, all operators are building their 5G networks.

Several national funded 5G testing projects are ongoing in Finland. Business Finland's 5thGEAR programme has created an ecosystem for testing of services and networks. The operator 5GTNF (5G Test Network Finland) has been established for the test network projects, and coordinates collaboration between test environments and the construction of a common test network.

5G Momentum, managed by Traficom, the Finnish Meteorological Institute and the Finnish Transport Infrastructure Agency, is an ecosystem established in 2018 to enable Finland to reach its goal of becoming world leader in 5G Technology, and promotes the development and implementation of 5G services.

Maritime:

- a) **Sea For Value (S4V):** nationally funded project aiming at increased level of maritime autonomy. The project prepares for advanced autonomous operations, by ensuring safe, sustainable and efficient channel for ships to enter and leave harbours.
- b) **Digirail (digrata.fi):** Study of the Finnish authorities regarding the future of rail, and the deployment of ERTMS. The study decided that ETCS Level 2 is best placed to replace the current train protection system, meaning that Finland must begin to use the FRMCS [37]. The goal is to begin extensive establishment of the system in 2028 [37].

Finland is involved in multiple **CEF projects**, related to the investment in the Trans-European Network for Transport. Some examples, which may have relevance for the 5G-ROUTES project include:

- a) **NordicWay project** regarding the deployment of C-ITS services in the Nordic countries Finland (nordicway.net);
- b) **Twin-Port 4 project** for upgrading the MoS (Motorway of the Seas) link between the ports of Helsinki and Tallinn, connecting the North Sea-Baltic to the Scandinavian-Mediterranean Core network corridors.

6. Availability of existing Infrastructure

6.1 General requirements for cross border trials

5G-ROUTES cross border trials in North East Europe are planned between Estonia and Latvia. A special focus is given to autonomous trials on TEN-T motorway network. Although North Europe is sparsely populated and it has low intensity of motorway network in terms of kilometres (km) of motorway per 1 000 km² of land area (Figure 24). Nevertheless, border crossings of these motorways facilitate international traffic flow of passengers and freight between EU Member States.

Figure 24. Motorway density per 1 000 km² of land area (EUROSTAT 2018)

According to the EU White paper on deployment of 5G network, the TEN-T networks should become operational by 2025, depending on national deployment plan. Both for Latvia and Estonia three distinctive EU category motorways identified as priorities are: A1/E67; A2/E77 and A3/E264. Motorway A1 having direct linkage to North–South goods flow, thus experiencing the most traffic intensity in region, while A2 has West-East corridor of goods connecting EU27 and Russia. Finally, A3 serves more regional Baltic connectivity needs.

Figure 25. Latvia – Estonia TEN-T road border crossings

The three plausible motorway options for cross border test beds should be evaluated for deployment of 5G connectivity trials. As summarised in Table 10 several advantages are associated with A3 Valga/Valka crossing, where existing railway connection and dense network of MNO base stations are among the strongpoints for selection of this scenario. Moreover, a fourth scenario – virtual border crossing in Bikernieki race track is included in comparison matrix of Table 10.

Table 10. Comparison matrix among several border crossing scenarios

Scenario	Road category	Railway connection	Operational customs	Nr. Of Base station in R= 2km LMT (LV)	Nr. Of Base station in R= 2km TELIA (EE)
A3/E264 Valka /Valga	TEN-T	Yes	no	3	6
A2/E77 Veclaicene /Murati	TEN-T	No	no	1	1
A1/E67 Ainaži /Ikla	TEN-T	RailBaltic (2030?)	yes	1	1
Virtual border – Bikernieki	Racetrack	N.A.	N.A.	16	TBC.

One of the key enabling technologies for deployment of 5G connectivity is fibre optical broad band –transport network. For MNO`s it is not mandatory to have fibre optical link to serve current commercial LTE technology, while advancement in 5G is directly linked with low latency requirements. Both Latvia and Estonia have heavily

invested in last mile optical fibre network. Estonian side has installed connectivity along border and all three border crossings are connected. From Latvian side rural urban area of Ainaži and Valka has optical connectivity. Veclaicene is remote for current investment policy.

Optical connectivity map of Estonia and Latvia is given in Figure 26 and Figure 27.

Figure 26. Estonia – in situ optical broadband network

Figure 27. Latvia – in situ optical broadband network

6.2 Assessment of cross border road infrastructure for autonomous trials

Assessment of existing road infrastructure should be lined with traffic intensity and traffic regulations. Among other aspects the traffic intensity per hour and number of crossing junctions within first 2 to 5 km should be analysed. Moreover, in case of “closing” the road an alternative route analysis is essential for autonomous trials on public roads within given project timeline. A set of matching indicators for individual use cases is aligned with existing regulations in Table 11. Comparing each border crossing route indicators for further risk assessment.

Table 11. Comparing of each border crossing route [21], [22]

	Crossing speed limit	Road visual sign of view	Junctions within 2km range	Excessive Road width	Hourly traffic average (cars/per hour) LV side	Average car speed Km/h (LV)	Monthly traffic average (cars/per day) EE side
A1/E67 Ainaži /Ikla	70/50	2+ km of straight road in grasslands	6	no	276	81*	4470
A2/E77 Veclačene /Murati	90	2+ km of straight road in forest	6	2 x 250m	138	104	828
A3/E264 Valka /Valga	50	Circular road, L-junction in urban area	12	150 m	90	95**	3771
Virtual crossing Bikernieki race track	100	Closed race track, with safety installations	N.A.	yes	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.

As shown in Figure 28, Figure 29 and Figure 30 several junctions are along the border road. For legal reasons, a correlation with number of junctions and traffic safety risks can be drawn. Therefore, in a future risk assessment in negotiation process with road authorities this aspect should be considered before the final decision of the trial road and use case implementation.

Figure 28. A1/E67 Ainaži/Ikla border crossing

Figure 29. A2/E77 Veclaicene/Murati border crossing

Figure 30. A3/E264 Valka/Valga border crossing

Both Ikla/Ainaži and Murati/Veclaicene crossings possess long straight road - an advantage compared with Valga/Valka scenario. It should be noted that rail connection in Valga/Valka border crossing has utmost importance from project perspective. Therefore, opportunities and risks will be evaluated carefully.

6.3 Assessment of MNO infrastructure within border crossing region

An assessment of MNO's existing infrastructure in vicinity of border crossing is essential for drawing a full picture for future connectivity and other issues like energy power charging, storage, and alike. A serving tower map for each border crossing by both Telia (EE) and LMT (LV) are summarised in Figure 30, Figure 31 and Figure 32. Each crossing has its individual set of features. For Ikla/Ainaži Telia (EE) coverage network is built on parallel to Via Baltica focusing on urban area of Ikla. LMT has sparsely deployed infrastructure linked with Via Baltica motorway A1/E67.

Figure 30. NO infrastructure near A1/E67 Ainaži/Ikla border crossing [23]

Murati/Veclaicene border crossing has sparsely deployed coverage tower network build near by A2/E77 motorway. As this crossing is in a remote area there is a set of challenges for deployment of 5G as a business case. Nevertheless, if some of the existing challenges could be addressed by deploying MEC, this may result in technically challenging, however, rewarding capability demonstration case for remote rural areas.

Figure 31. MNO infrastructure near A2/E77 Veclaicene/Murati border crossing [23]

Finally, A3 Valga/Valka border crossing as urban area has a relatively dense network infrastructure coverage. Borderline is wavered in this area resulting in interference in surrounding area. Signal intensity and interference issues should be analysed before deployment of 5G solutions in this area.

Figure 32. MNO infrastructure near A3/E264 Valka/Valga border crossing [23]

6.4 Assessment of virtual cross border road infrastructure for autonomous trials

A virtual border crossing on Bīķernieki racetrack has been identified as potential trial site during planning process and when facing technical issues in regard to defined use cases (Figure 33). An utmost advantage of race track deployment as a virtual border crossing trials are - controlled road risks. The agreement with track owner "CSDD Latvia" has been signed on Dec. 18 allowing to start the trials in early 2021. Central location of LMT infrastructure is an enabler for a quick set up of 5G infrastructure. A discussion with radio spectrum authority has been initiated

for deployment of shared bandwidth of LMT between both MNO partners namely LMT (LV) and Telia (EE). An interpretation of two operator sectorial network deployment is depicted in Figure 34.

Initial assumptions on 5G network deployment are aligned with availability of the racetrack for the trials. First option considers start/ finish straight allowing maximum platooning speed thus testing handover efficiency. The second option considers a full cycle allowing to quantify and to perform a non-stop trial looping and assessing connectivity. A strong commitment for establishing 5G multi-MNO - virtual crossing border racetrack is set for the first quarter of 2021. Exploring entire racetrack length for connectivity will be evaluated in upcoming years due requests of partners involved in several use cases.

Figure 33. Virtual cross border – Bikernieki race track

Figure 34. Eventual virtual border crossing between Telia and LMT on Bikernieki race track

6.5 Latvia – Estonia rail cross border connectivity

Only one option is available for a cross border rail-road connectivity deployment between Latvia and Estonia. Although the Pan-European railway line RailBaltica is under the construction with devoted 5G infrastructure this connection will not become available for tests within 5G-ROUTES project timeframe. A scheduled rail connection runs from Riga to Valga by partner AS Pasažieru Vilciens. From Valga it continues to Tartu by partner Elron. A demo case will be deployed between Valga and connected station - Lugaži (LV). Usual travel time between Lugaži and Valga is approx. 6 min for 4km of distance. As shown in Figure 35. The MNO infrastructure is densely deployed in Valka/Valga region, therefore a relatively rapid deployment of 5G connectivity could be expected in 2021.

Figure 35. Rail connection Valka/Valga

6.6 Estonian – Finnish sea cross border connectivity

A new level of connectivity challenges will be addressed at Tallinn (EE) and Helsinki (FI) (from Muuga to Vuosaari seaports) sea border crossing of ferries on open sea (Figure 36). The distance between both capitals is approx. 80km - a stretch for 5G connectivity. Tourists and cargo are two separate flows to address during the demonstration activity. Several scenarios are to be evaluated including handover by satellite communication provided by partner Airbus. Among currently considered scenarios is one where connectivity is provided from shore to ferry considering open field dimming of the signal. Alternative scenario involves setting up 5G station on the ferry. Each scenario has several drawbacks and several interactions for tackling technical solution by end of 2021.

Figure 36. Ferry crossing of Tallinn/Helsinki sea border

6.7 Satellite 5G connectivity

Goal of this section is to provide a summary of the status of 5G satellite connectivity, an assessment of which space assets may be used for the 5G-ROUTES trials and a brief outlook on future deployments.

With the earliest beginnings in the 1960s satellite communications have been the first commercial utilization of space – providing international and long-haul telephone services and becoming the primary means for distributing TV programs around the world. Today fixed and mobile satellite communications are supporting mainly two types of applications:

- The high data-rate and -volume bulk traffic supported by high-throughput satellites (mainly from Geostationary Orbit) and
- The low data-rate and –volume IoT traffic mostly employing smaller satellites in Low Earth Orbit

Section 2.3 of 5G-ROUTES deliverable D1.1 [1] gives an overview of satellite communication networks and their characteristics.

The implementation of the next generation 5G networks foresee in its 3GPP standardization effort the integration of non-terrestrial networks - i.e. the 3rd dimension including aerial and satellite nodes – as an integral part of the 5G ecosystem. Satellites can well serve two of the three corners of the triangle of 5G usage scenarios (see section 2.1 of 5G-ROUTES deliverable D1.1 [1]):

- enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) - corresponding to the high data-rate/-volume applications that are relevant to communications for flying vehicles (passenger aircraft, UAVs, UAMs) domains discussed above. Due to the throughput requirements these applications will typically require larger more complex satellites of at least 100 – 200 kgs or even significantly higher.
- massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) - corresponding to the low data-rate/-volume applications that are relevant to the Aerial Cloud Domain that will be described in the following section. For these applications nanosatellites (cubesats) of only 10-20 kgs are considered.
- While ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (uRLLC) cannot be served well by satellites – due to latencies of at least multiple 10s of milliseconds due to the transmission path length via space. To reduce latency as far as possible Low Earth Orbit constellations are increasingly "en vogue" for both eMBB and mMTC applications.

6.7.1 Status of 5G NTN

Non-terrestrial networks are networks (or their segments) that use spaceborne or airborne vehicles for transmission. 3GPP TS 22.261 [2] - approved at SA#82 - mandates in its section 6.3.2.3 among other things that:

- The 5G system shall be able to provide services using satellite access
- A 5G system with satellite access shall support different configurations where the radio access network is either a satellite NG-RAN or a non-3GPP satellite access network, or both.
- A UE supporting satellite access shall be able to provide or assist in providing its location to the 5G network.
- A 5G system with satellite access shall be able to determine a UE's location to provide service (e.g. route traffic, support emergency calls) in accordance with the governing national or regional regulatory requirements applicable to that UE.

As a consequence a number of activities - i.e. study and work items - were defined and have successively been carried out to support Non-terrestrial networks by identifying suitable use cases [3], exploring the different technical aspects [4] and deriving solutions for New radio to support NTN [5].

These activities have culminated into a proposal for a work item [7] to draft a first specification for NTN within 5G for release 17 that was approved at RAN#86. With this the process for Non-terrestrial networks to become

an integral part of the 5G ecosystem has been advanced significantly. Based on this specification - that is due with the finalization of release 17 by the end of 2021 - equipment vendors will be able to develop suitable chip sets, components, and units.

Given this timeline, a full implementation of 5GNTN will not be ready for trials within 5G-ROUTES. However, 3GPP foresees an Inter Working Functionality [6] through which legacy satellite connectivity can be integrated with 5G core networks. The concept that will be used as the baseline for demonstrating the utility of satellite connectivity in for selected 5G-ROUTES use cases is shown in Figure 37.

Figure 37. Satellite connectivity integration with 5G core network via N3IWF

6.7.2 Satellite systems for satellite connectivity and 5G NTN

No dedicated deployment of 5G ready satellites can be achieved within the 5G-ROUTES project. Therefore, demonstrations and field trials on satellite connectivity must rely on the space assets that are available and can be accessed in the relevant time frame - i.e. late 2021 to early 2023. The following assets will be already in orbit at the time of the 5G-ROUTES trials and are being considered:

- Operational Geostationary satellites - there is a significant number of GEO satellites in orbit, that operate different frequency bands - from L-Band (1 - 2 GHz) and S-Band (2 - 4 GHz), via C-Band (4 - 8 GHz) to Ku-Band (10 - 16 GHz) and Ka-Band (17 - 30 GHz). Higher frequencies allow for higher data rates, so Ku-/Ka-Band satellites are suitable for eMBB applications, while L-/S-Band are only suitable for mMTC. A problem for GEO satellites is the limited visibility and coverage at higher latitudes as well as the unfavourable link budget due to the satellites being at about 35600 km above the Earth surface.
- Operational LEO satellites - there are a few satellite constellations in lower Earth orbit (below 1500km altitude) that can provide coverage even at higher latitudes and the poles and have a much more beneficial link budget. Iridium current market leader for worldwide voice and data services to satellite phones, pagers, and integrated transceivers in the L-Band. It has just completed renewal of its constellation.
- LEO prototype or test satellites - in order to prepare for future deployments there are a number of prototype satellites - typically in LEO due to cost considerations - that have been placed in orbit in the last few years or are planned to be launched soon. Most prominently, Canadian operator Telesat has

used its two LEO Vantage satellite to demonstrate 5G backhaul connections in Ka-Band with partner University of Surrey [8].

- Emerging LEO mega-constellations - both Starlink and OneWeb constellations already have a significant number of satellites in orbit (Starlink > 700, OneWeb > 30) and have scheduled further launches to complete their constellations in the coming year(s). They have announced the operational provision of first services - operating in the Ku-Band - beginning already in late 2021 and thus could potentially be used for 5G-ROUTES trials.

6.7.3 Options for Satellite connectivity in 5G-ROUTES

The baseline for demonstrating satellite connectivity in 5G-ROUTES as envisioned during the proposal stage, was to employ a suitable GEO satellite in Ku-Band for eMBB services and to use Iridium L-Band services for mMTC applications. Beyond that further options that will be further investigated in preparation of the road trials are listed in Table 12. Especially, demonstrating satellite connectivity through one of the emerging mega-constellations could provide an innovative glimpse into the future of integrated terrestrial-satellite connectivity in 5G and beyond.

Table 12. Satellite connectivity options for 5G-ROUTES trials (green: baseline, orange: optional)

Frequency Band	Satellite System	Orbit	Usage	Data rate	Remarks
Ku	Intelsat 33e or 905	GEO	eMBB	> 1 Mbps	KALO service commercially available via Intelsat or other GEO satellite, antenna/modem available
L	Iridium	LEO	mMTC	Few kbps	Commercial service, antenna/modem available
S	Echostar 21	GEO	mMTC+	100 kbps	Contact with Echostar Mobile established, interest in collaboration,
Ku	OneWeb	LEO	eMBB	> 1 Mbps	SW Adaption of available antenna/modem necessary
Ku	Starlink	LEO	eMBB	> 1 Mbps	SW Adaption of available antenna/modem necessary
Ka	Telesat	LEO	eMBB	> 1 Mbps	Contact with supplier for suitable antenna established

6.7.4 Outlook on future deployments

The implementation of 5G NTN will transform the satellite communications industry. Satellite connectivity will become part of the mainstream telecommunications ecosystems. As the 3GPP standard for 5G New Radio defines a mode for direct access to Non-Terrestrial Networks. The same device that connects to a ground base station will also allow connections to satellites without modification - leading to a dramatic cost reduction for satellite access. Therefore, it can be expected that future satellite systems to be deployed beyond 2025 will conform to the 5G NTN standard. An assessment of the expected future developments and deployments will be conducted in the updated version of this document (deliverable D1.4).

7. 5G-ROUTES network deployment plan

Maturity of 5G technologies and commercial solution readiness for deployment of 5G networks are still in development phase. Therefore, an initial deployment of 5G-ROUTES trial network solution plan is based on CAM features already available from 3GPP Release 15. A challenge ahead is to formulate deployment plan with realistic timeline respecting delays of Release 16 and 17 and its consequences providing commercial solutions for vendors to procure and deploy RN equipment. A deployment plan should align several primarily unrelated events and settings to enable initial trials of use cases. In current vision a flowchart type of plan is drawn pinning use case features, service requirements above timeline up to end of the project.

7.1 Network requirements

Network requirements and subsequent network planning are affiliated with use case requirements. These requirements will be monitored by network and service KPIs which should be achieved. KPI's are derived from other deliverable D.1.1. contributed by 5G-ROUTES partners contributing to success of particular use case. Five main features and they relevance to use cases are structured as 3GPP Rel-16 specific – MEC, Cellular V2X and 5G Satellite while 3GPP Rel-17 specific are NR Positioning and Network slicing. Assumption of feature list by use cases shown in Table 13.

Table 13. 5G Feature list by use cases (Assumption)

Nr	Use Case	5G satellite	Network slicing	MEC	Cellular V2X	NR Positioning
1.1	Dynamic vehicles platooning		X	X	X	X
1.2	Cooperative lane change		X	X	X	X
1.3	See-Through view for safe automated overtake		X	X	X	
2.1	Intersection collision control				X	
2.2	Traffic jam chauffeur				X	
3.1	Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness		X	X	X	
3.2	Connected maintenance		X			
3.3	VRU collision avoidance				X	
4.1	360 degree immersive multi-user gaming on the go	X				
4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the move	X				
5.1	Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics	X				
5.2	5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight		X	X		
5.3	FRMCS telemetry operation	X				

5G connectivity trial sites will be covered with Large macro, Macro and Micro cells. Classification of use-cases by radio service type is described in D1.1 “Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM” and summary is shown in Table 14.

Table 14. Radio service requirements by use case

Nr	Use Case	Large macro	Macro	Micro
1.1	Dynamic vehicles platooning		X	
1.2	Cooperative lane change		X	
1.3	See-Through view for safe automated overtake		X	
2.1	Intersection collision control		X	X
2.2	Traffic jam chauffeur		X	
3.1	Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness		X	
3.2	Connected maintenance		X	
3.3	VRU collision avoidance		X	
4.1	360 degree immersive multi-user gaming on the go			X
4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the move			X
5.1	Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics	X	X	
5.2	5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight	X	X	
5.3	FRMCS telemetry operation		X	X

7.2 Deployment options & scenarios

Multiple connectivity options in the 3GPP architecture for 5G have created several possible deployment alternatives shown in Table 15 and Figure 38. Initial focus for non-standalone (NSA) deployment are on Option 4 and Option 7, the main difference is which radio access technology (RAT) is used as main: Option 4 – NR and Option 7 – LTE. Option 2 is Standalone (SA) option and represents a 5G NR access deployed in the network and connected to the 5GC. This option is most suitable for MNO, if it wants to offer 5G only service without 4G inter-working. This option is considered as main for 5G deployment in 5G-ROUTES project. This type of deployment option will allow to implement and test all types of use cases: mMTC, eMBB and URLLC provided it has the necessary spectrum allocated of each type of service [24]. There are several more options described by 3GPP [28], but these won't be considered in project realization. Overall summary of options in Table 15 and Figure 38.

Table 15. 5G deployment options

Option	Core Network	Master RAT	Secondary RAT	Type
Option 3	EPC	LTE	NR	NSA
Option 2	5GC	NR	-	SA
Option 4	5GC	NR	eLTE	NSA
Option 5	5GC	eLTE	-	SA
Option 7	5GC	eLTE	NR	NSA

Figure 38. 5G deployment options [28]

Network slicing is one of the key features which will be deployed, and which is crucial to achieve KPIs of some of the use cases. Network slicing architecture differentiates based on use case type: eMBB, URLLC and mMTC as shown in preliminary architecture options in Figure 39.

Figure 39. E2E Network slicing architecture options

7.3 Eventual core & radio network architecture

Initial vision of high-level network architecture at Bikernieki racetrack is shown in Figure 40. Bikernieki racetrack is considered as first test bed for rapid deployment and feasibility assessment of virtual border crossing. Future improvements in Core & RAN for network handover on actual border crossings will be tested.

Figure 40. Initial Bikernieki racetrack network architecture

7.4 Timeline

A timeline example summarising, field trials of 5G connectivity features on timescale of 2021 up to 2024 are given in Figure 41. A timing is assumed based on non-future delays associated with 3GPP release incorporation in vendor supply chain. This assumption should be taken with caution and reassessed throughout the project with instant reassessment with partners involved in demonstration use case.

Figure 41. 5G-ROUTES deployment timeline (EXAMPLE)

8. Conclusions

The Deliverable gives an overview of existing infrastructure, legislative, technology readiness and includes the first analysis of sites where tests of use cases will be performed. All Latvia-Estonia cross-border options on the TEN-T motorway network roads have been identified and taken into account. Challenges and opportunities of each option are still under discussion, but on the basis of first findings, the need for an additional test site was identified.

Bikernieki racetrack located in Riga will be used as proof-of-concept testbed to validate predefined requirements of CCAM use cases. Unlike the rest of test sites, virtual cross-border simulation and standalone 5G networks will be deployed in Bikernieki provided by LMT and Telia. By conducting particular exercise, the maturity level of Core and RAN architecture has been reached identifying missing and weak links of current assumptions. Within current deployment scenario a 5G CAM trials could start already in second quarter of 2021.

It could be concluded that initial 5G-ROUTES network deployment plan has been started drawn with example of eventual timeline. Near future readiness of eventual features required for demonstration of particular use cases are highlighted. The deployment plan will be refined in the upcoming months (by M10) when there will be more clear view on KPIs defined by each use case.

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